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SONNET – SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY TRANSITIONS

Co-creating a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, success and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector

D5.4 (D23):

Report on assessment of future potentials of SIE in Europe: Business models and competitiveness, future policy interventions

Project Coordinator: Fraunhofer ISI (Karoline Rogge)

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Leader Organisation: GEM

Author/s: Marie-Charlotte Guetlein and Joachim Schleich

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Responsible scientist/administrator:	Marie-Charlotte Guetlein (GEM), Joachim Schleich (GEM)
Contributor(s):	Marie-Charlotte Guetlein (GEM), Joachim Schleich (GEM)
Internal reviewer(s):	Agata Dembek (ALK), Benjamin Sovacool (UoS), Karoline Rogge (ISI)

PROJECT PARTNERS

No	Participant name	Short Name	Country code	Partners' logos
1	Fraunhofer Society, with its Fraunhofer Institute of Systems and Innovation Research (Fraunhofer ISI)	ISI	DE	Fraunhofer ISI
2	Dutch Research Institute for Transitions	DRIFT	NL	
3	University of Sussex, with its Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU)	UoS	UK	
4	Grenoble Ecole de Management	GEM	FR	
5	Akademia Leona Kozminkiego	ALK	PL	
6	Zuercher Hochschule for Applied Research	ZHAW	CH	
7	ICLEI European Secretariat	ICLEI	DE	
8	City of Mannheim	MANN	GER	
9	City of Antwerp	ANTW	BE	
10	City of Bristol	BRIS	UK	
11	City of Grenoble	GRENOBLE	FR	
12	City of Warsaw	WARS	PL	
13	City of Basel (Associated Partner)	BASE	CH	

Executive Summary

SONNET aims to create an inter- and transdisciplinary understanding of the diversity and processes of social innovations in the energy sector (SIE) using an innovative mixed-method research design. As part of work package 5 of the SONNET project, the citizen survey gathers responses from approximately 6,000 participants in three countries: France, Germany, and Poland. The surveys consist of a general part and a specific part focussing on selected SIE.

Based on a demographically representative citizen survey in France, Germany and Poland (total N= 6,141), this report assesses future potential of SIE in European countries. To this end, it employs statistical-econometric analyses to investigate factors driving citizen investment in renewable energy projects, participation in renewable energy cooperatives, and purchasing of mobile energy applications with gamification components. These analyses rely in particular on three stated preferences discrete choice experiments (DCEs) on (i) investment projects in decentralised renewable electricity generation conducted in France, Germany, and Poland, (ii) participation in renewable energy cooperatives (RECs) conducted in France, and (iii) energy gamification through mobile applications conducted in Germany. The analysis identifies the role of specific attributes of these SIEs, and individual characteristics such as attitudes and socio-demographic factors. Based on the results and insights from additional survey questions, recommendations for business models and policies are derived.

Our findings suggest that around 90% of participants in France, Germany and Poland choose to invest in one of the projects shown in our DCE on investments in decentralized renewable electricity generation. Similarly, 79% of respondents in France choose to invest in at least one of the energy cooperatives shown to them in our DCE on RECs. These findings suggest a generally high interest in this kind of projects - and thus a strong future potential for their diffusion. At the same time, it is unlikely that most citizens will invest in renewable electricity generation projects in the near future. In a related survey question, between 20 and 29% of respondents in France, Germany and Poland indicated that they were planning to invest in a green/sustainable crowdfunding project, in a REC or in green/sustainable investment assets. Regarding our DCE on energy gamification through mobile apps, our findings suggest that around 65% of participants in Germany choose to purchase at least one of the energy apps shown to them. These figures are considerably lower compared to the share of participants who selected at least one of the investment options in the DCE on renewable electricity production projects (89% on average) and in the DCE on RECs (79%). They suggest that interest in the type of mobile energy apps proposed in our DCE is comparatively weak, despite the low cost of the apps.

Looking at attributes of SIE, we observe that financial aspects play an important role for citizens' decision to invest in renewable electricity generation projects or RECs. Respondents prefer projects with higher rates of return, lower probability that the investment is lost, and lower minimum investment requirements. In France and Germany, we also observe a preference for matching of citizen investments by the municipality. The DCE conducted in France further reveals that respondents, on average, prefer RECs without involvement of firms and with a one-member-one-vote decision rule. Respondents also value the possibility to delegate their voting rights to a proxy and show a strong preference for higher rates of self-consumption of the produced electricity. The experiment on gamification through mobile apps in Germany shows

that respondents generally dislike subscription fees, but that the negative effect of subscription fees on adoption can be moderated if subscription fees are used for charitable donations. We further observe that respondents value app features, including expert advice, nudges (social comparison feedback), and gamification components (competition).

Regarding individual characteristics, we observe that participants who have a stronger environmental identity and participants whose perception of social pressure to participate in SIE is stronger are more likely to choose a renewable electricity generation project, a REC, or an energy app in our DCEs. Capabilities also play a significant role for citizen participation in SIE: respondents with an above-median score of financial literacy and prior experience with sustainable investments are more likely to invest in renewable electricity generation projects or RECs in our DCEs. Similarly, respondents with experience with energy apps or paid apps are more likely to choose an energy app over the opt-out option in the DCE in Germany. Other individual-specific factors that are correlated with participation in SIE include risk preferences, local identity, positive reciprocity, social-comparison orientation, competitive orientation, and satisfaction with government policies. Moreover, we observe that in all three DCEs older participants are more likely to choose an opt-out option. Income has a positive effect on participation in renewable electricity generation projects and RECs, but not on the adoption of apps.

Our findings have direct implications for business models and policies. The observed preferences for specific attributes provide indications for business models that are likely to be more successful and/or should be enabled by policies. Our insights on individual characteristics allow to discern citizens who are more likely to engage in specific SIE types and to identify policies that could help increase citizens' willingness to engage in these SIE.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Social innovations in the energy sector (SIE) have gained increasing interest from both academics and civil society actors by enabling sustainable energy transitions and also as a relevant field of experience and learning (Fressoli et al., 2014). SONNET aims to contribute to the comprehension of these processes by generating novel understandings of the diversity, processes and contributions of social innovation in the energy sector, and critically evaluating and assessing their success and future potential towards supporting sustainable transitions of energy systems.

WP5 aims to quantitatively examine citizen's individual perceptions of socio-economic, socio-cultural and socio-political enabling and impeding conditions of SIE and their acceptance to develop a better understanding of the potential scope and diffusion of SIE necessary for sustainable energy transitions. To this end, a demographically representative survey was implemented among ca. 6,000 participants in France, Germany, and Poland.

The SONNET citizen survey, which is described in detail in D5.1, consists of a general part and a specific part. The general part elicits information on household and individual characteristics of citizens (income, gender, environmental identity, etc.), acceptance of different types of SIE, and attitudes and behaviours regarding clean energy, energy technologies, policy mixes, etc. The key descriptive findings of the general part of the survey are reported in Deliverable D5.2. The specific part of the SONNET citizen survey consists of three discrete choice experiments (DCEs) on (i) investment projects in decentralised renewable electricity generation conducted in France, Germany, and Poland, (ii) participation in renewable energy cooperatives (RECs) conducted in France, and (iii) energy gamification through mobile applications conducted in Germany. It further includes an experiment on information treatments in the context of campaigns against specific energy pathways in Poland. D5.3 presents results from the four experiments.

This deliverable D5.4 assesses the future potentials of SIE in European countries. To this end, D5.4 employs statistical-econometric analyses to investigate factors driving citizen investment in renewable energy projects, participation in renewable energy cooperatives, and purchasing of mobile energy applications with gamification components. These analyses rely on the SONNET citizen survey including the three DCEs. The analysis identifies the role of selected attributes of these SIEs, and individual characteristics such as attitudes and socio-demographic factors.¹ In addition, we use survey items included in the sample in France to assess the relevance of factors that would motivate participants to invest in a REC in the future. The DCE results and survey items are discussed in light of insights from the SONNET WP3 report on energy cooperatives in France (Ranville and Vernay, 2020). Similarly, we use survey items included in the sample in Germany to assess factors that would motivate participants to download an energy app. Based on the results from the statistical-econometric analyses, D5.4 derives recommendations for business models and policies.

¹ The analyses in D5.4 differ from the analyses in D5.3. D5.3. focused on the attributes of the SIE only and did not consider the role of individual characteristic.

This report is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the methodology, including the survey outline and data collection procedure, and the econometric methods. The description of the survey outline and data collection procedure is taken, largely verbatim, from D5.2. The description of the econometric methods is partly taken from D5.3 but diverges on core aspects as the econometric methods used in D5.4 differ from those used in D5.3. Sections 3, 4 and 5 include detailed descriptions of the samples and choice experiment designs for each of the three DCEs. These sections also present results from the econometric analyses of the DCEs. Descriptions of samples and choice experiment designs, which are necessary to correctly interpret results, have been taken, largely verbatim, from D5.3. Wording used to describe results is taken in parts from D5.3 as results for choice attributed are consistent across D5.4 and D5.3. Based on the results presented in sections 3, 4, and 5, section 6 discusses future potential of the respective SIEs and considers implications for business models and policies using results from the DCEs and related survey questions in the samples in France and Germany.

2 METHODOLOGY

The present report is based on data collected through the SONNET citizen survey implemented in France, Germany, and Poland. This section presents the survey outline and data collection procedure, as well as the econometric methods used.

2.1 Survey and data collection

The SONNET citizen survey starts with an introduction informing participants about survey procedures, anonymity, privacy and data protection, as well as their right to withdraw at any time. The introduction is followed by the screening questions related to the age, gender, region, and income of participants to ensure that quota requirements are met and that only qualified participants take part. The screening questions are followed by the specific survey part on selected SIE types, including the DCEs. The subsequent general part of the survey includes questions related to citizens' willingness to participate in SIE, questions on attitudes towards policies and policy objectives, questions on general political orientation and trust in institutions, questions on individual behaviours (including environmental behaviours), attitudes, and preferences (including social preferences such as social-comparison orientation or preferences for reciprocity). A more detailed description of the survey design is provided in D5.1. Key descriptive findings from the general part can be found in D5.2.

The survey questionnaire was implemented via the Qualtrics software. Prior to fielding the survey, extensive pre-tests were carried out with the English version and the responses obtained were used to test the length of the questionnaire and participants' understanding of the different tasks and questions.² Some adjustments in wording and design of experiments were made before the final questionnaire was translated from English into national languages by professional translators. Translations were cross-checked by scientists from the project team for quality control. The actual survey was then administered in France, Germany, and Poland through existing household panels of Norstat, a professional market research institute, via subcontracting. To allow for meaningful statistical results, a minimum sample size of approximately 2,000 observations per country was used. In each country, participants were selected via quota sampling using quotas for gender, age, region and income based on official EU or national statistics. In this sense, the surveys are demographically representative. To incentivize participation in the survey each participant who completed the survey received a small reward through Norstat's point system. Interviews were carried out in July and August 2021. The median response time across all three countries was about 20 minutes.

To ensure that quota requirements were met, participants answered screening questions on age (4-5 splits), gender, region (NUTS 2 or similar) and income (3 splits). Questions were formulated

² For budget reasons, all pre-tests were carried out using the English version. Only the final version of the survey was translated to French, German and Polish. Pre-tests were conducted with respondents from the UK that were recruited through the Prolific Academic platform.

according to the quotas provided by GEM and based on official EU or national statistics. Participants who did not fulfil the quota requirements received a message informing them that they were not eligible to participate and were automatically directed back to the survey institute's website.

The survey contained two quality control questions. In both questions, participants were asked to check a particular option among all options available. Participants who failed to check the indicated option in both control questions were excluded from the survey and informed that their answers did not fulfil the quality standards.

Participants were treated as speeders when the duration to complete the survey was less than 1/3 of the median time. Speeders were excluded from the analysis. The final number of participants considered in this deliverable was 2,096 in France (excluding 62 speeders), 1,997 in Germany (excluding 52 speeders), and 2,048 in Poland (excluding 54 speeders) for a total sample of 6,141.

2.2 Econometric Methods

Participants in the three DCEs are asked repeatedly to choose one option or alternative from a set of options or alternatives presented to them. For example, in the DCE implemented in France, Germany and Poland, participants are shown repeatedly two different renewable electricity generation projects and are asked to indicate in which of the two projects – if any – they would like to invest. A set of alternatives presented to participants is also called a choice set.

In all three DCEs, the alternatives in the choice sets differ on selected attributes including benefits / desirable features (e.g. rate of return, social comparison feedback) and costs / undesirable features (e.g. subscription fees, probability that the investment is lost). By choosing an alternative from a choice set participants make trade-offs between these attributes. Each of our three DCEs consists of 24 choice sets with two choice alternatives each. To reduce cognitive burden, the choice sets are divided into three blocks of eight choice sets and participants in the DCE are randomly assigned to one block. Thus, each participant makes eight consecutive choices between two alternatives. The attributes and an example of a choice set for each DCE are presented in section 3, 4 and 5, respectively.

The DCE methodology is consistent with random utility theory (RUT) (McFadden, 1974). As described by Louviere et al. (2010, p. 62), *“RUT proposes that there is a latent construct called “utility” existing in a person’s head that cannot be observed by researchers. That is, a person has a “utility” for each choice alternative, but these utilities cannot be “seen” by researchers, which is why they are termed “latent”. RUT assumes that the latent utilities can be summarized by two components, a systematic (explainable) component and a random (unexplainable) component. Systematic components comprise attributes explaining differences in choice alternatives and covariates explaining differences in individuals’ choices. Random components comprise all unidentified factors that impact choices.”*

Consistent with McFadden's choice model (McFadden, 1974), we express the latent utility function of respondent i choosing alternative j in choice set t as

$$U_{ijt} = \beta X_{ijt} + \alpha_i Z_i + \varepsilon_{ijt}, \quad i = 1, \dots, I, j = 1, \dots, J, t = 1, \dots, T \quad (1)$$

X_{ijt} is a vector comprised of alternative-specific variables, reflecting the attribute levels of alternative j in choice set t that respondent i faces. Z_i is a vector of respondent-specific characteristics that do not vary across alternatives or choice sets. Finally, ε_{ijt} is a vector of error terms that are assumed to be independent Gumbel-type extreme-value random variables, leading to a fixed-effects logit model.

In each choice set t , respondent i chooses the alternative j that maximizes her utility in equation (1). The choice sets in our DCEs always comprise of two investment alternatives, A and B, and an opt-out option, O. This implies that a respondent i chooses the opt-out option in any given choice set t if and only if $U_{iAt} < U_{iOt}$ and $U_{iBt} < U_{iOt}$. Based on the observed choices between alternatives and the opt-out option in our DCEs, we fit the choice model in equation (1) using the *cmlogit* command in Stata 17.0. We further calculate average discrete and marginal effects of all alternative-specific and individual-specific variables on the probability of choosing an investment option over the opt-out option (Williams, 2012). Finally, the marginal willingness to pay (WTP) for an attribute x may be estimated as:

$$\widehat{WTP}_x = -\frac{\hat{\beta}_x}{\hat{\beta}_p} \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{\beta}_x$ is the estimated parameter associated with attribute x , and $\hat{\beta}_p$ is the estimated parameter associated with the cost attribute in the DCE.

2.3 Limitations

Our methodology has several limitations. First, while our sample is demographically representative of the population in terms of our quota requirements, the sample is not representative of the population in terms of other characteristics such as education or socio-professional category. While our multivariate analysis controls for many factors, we cannot exclude that unobserved factors influence our results which would limit their external validity. Moreover, respondents who were excluded from the survey because they failed the attention checks or because they were speeders might systematically differ from other respondents, e.g. in terms of their preferences for SIE and SIE attributes, thus biasing our results. Similarly, respondents who dropped out of the survey (around 400 in each country), might differ from respondents who completed the questionnaire, possibly leading to a self-selection bias in our results.

Second, our analyses rely on declarative survey questions and stated preferences rather than revealed behaviors and preferences. Our results might thus be subject to hypothetical bias. Our

DCE designs included two measures to mitigate the hypothetical bias inherent in DCEs. First, our framing included a so called 'cheap talk' script³ to produce more reliable estimates (Tonsor and Shupp, 2011). That is, respondents were asked to make their choices as they would likely make them in a real choice situation. Second, our design included an opt-out option. That is, in addition to the choice alternatives, respondents could always choose to select none of the proposed alternatives and opt-out. Despite these measures, hypothetical bias in the DCEs could have led to an overestimation of the share of respondents generally interested in the presented options – and by extrapolation of citizens' interest in specific SIE. Similarly, answers to survey questions eliciting respondent's preferences or attitudes might not be reliable. To ensure reliability as much as possible, we used established questions and scales whenever possible.

Third, our results pertain to the type of SIE initiatives shown in the DCEs and characterized by specific attributes and attribute levels. Respondents might have made different decisions if choice options were described differently. Thus, our results shed light on respondents' general interest in SIE initiatives similar to the options presented in the DCE and on their perception of specific attributes. However, findings should be used cautiously to form expectations about citizens' participation in SIE initiatives which differ from the options shown in the DCEs.

³“Cheap talk scripts were initially implemented by Cummings and Taylor (1999) in an attempt to reduce hypothetical bias by describing to participants, before making a decision, the propensity of respondents like themselves to exaggerate stated willingness to pay” (Tonsor and Shupp, 2011, p. 1015). Similar to the cheap talk scripts by Cummings and Taylor (1999) and Tonsor and Shupp (2011), our cheap talk scripts repeatedly ask respondents to make their decisions as they would in a real choice situation.

3 DISCRETE CHOICE EXPERIMENT ON INVESTMENT PROJECTS IN DECENTRALIZED ELECTRICITY GENERATION (FRANCE, GERMANY, POLAND)

Energy communities are considered to play an important role in the European energy transition as they promote the use of renewable energy and empower citizens to participate in the transformation of energy systems (e.g. Viardot, 2013, Hentschel et al., 2018). They are also believed to help democratize the energy sector (Yildiz, 2015) and to increase social acceptance of renewable energy projects (Musall, 2011; Bauwens et al., 2016).

In this section, we present and analyse this DCE on investment projects in decentralized electricity generation. We are particularly interested in attributes that might allow for a broader diffusion of such projects in the general population, and hence help increase the acceptance of the energy transition in these countries. In addition to standard attributes such as rate of return, our DCE includes project attributes which previous studies in related contexts have not examined (matching by municipalities and the risk of total loss) or only scarcely examined (use of profits).

This section is organized as follows. First, we provide more details on the sample. Then we describe the DCE design and report and discuss the results.

3.1 Sample

Excluding speeders and those who failed both attention checks, 2,096 participants in France, 1,997 participants in Germany, and 2,048 participants in Poland took part in our survey. In each country, approximately half the participants were randomly assigned to take part in the DCE on investment projects in decentralized electricity generation. Thus, 1,074 participants in France, 986 participants in Germany and 936 participants in Poland completed the DCE presented in this section.

Summary statistics for the three samples are displayed in Table 1. Table 1 also presents national population statistics for comparison. Due to varying income levels and different currencies, different categories were used in the three countries.⁴ Overall, sample statistics are close to national statistics. In France, participants below the age of 30 and participants in the highest household income category are slightly underrepresented. In Germany, participants in the age category 30-49 years are slightly overrepresented. Finally, in Poland, participants in the lowest household income category are slightly underrepresented compared to the national average.

⁴ 1 PLN corresponded to 22 EUR cent in 2021, thus the three income classes for Poland are segregated by around 650 EUR and 1290 EUR.

Table 1: Sample characteristics for participants in the DCE on investment projects in decentralized electricity generation

	France		Germany		Poland	
	Sample	Population	Sample	Population	Sample	Population
Share of males^a	49.9%	48.3%	49.0%	49.3%	48.1%	48.4%
Age (share of adult population)^b						
18-29	14.1%	17.6%	15.0%	16.5%	17.5%	17.4%
30-49	33.0%	32.3%	36.6%	30.3%	37.2%	36.9%
50-64	26.5%	24.5%	24.7%	27.3%	26.6%	24.1%
65 and older	26.4%	25.5%	23.6%	25.8%	18.6%	21.6%
Household income						
2,000 EUR or less ^c	38.6%	36%	-	-	-	-
2,001 – 4,000 EUR	40.7%	42%	-	-	-	-
More than 4,000 EUR	20.7%	23%	-	-	-	-
2,000 EUR or less ^d	-	-	31.6%	30%	-	-
2,001 – 3,600 EUR	-	-	28.3%	31%	-	-
More than 3,600 EUR	-	-	40.1%	39%	-	-
3,000 PLN or less ^e	-	-	-	-	24.7%	30%
3,001 – 5,900 PLN	-	-	-	-	41.5%	40%
More than 5,900 PLN	-	-	-	-	33.7%	30%

^a Source of population statistics: Eurostat (2020). ^b Source of population statistics: Eurostat (2019). ^c Source of population statistics: Insee (2017). ^d Source of population statistics: Statistisches Bundesamt (2018). ^e Source of population statistics: ESS (2020).

3.2 Discrete choice experiment design

We used the following framing to introduce the DCE on investment projects in decentralized electricity generation:⁵

"In this part of the survey, we invite you to make a series of hypothetical choices between different investment options. There are no right or wrong answers to these questions.

*Imagine you are being offered the opportunity to **buy a share in a renewable power plant** of your choice such as a windfarm, a solar power plant, or a biogas plant **located in your municipality**. If you chose to invest, you would have to pay the capital requirement for the investment up front. You get to own part of the renewable energy plant. The other shareholders of the plant are other citizens and the municipality. The plant sells carbon-free electricity into the electricity grid and makes money over time. **As payments, you annually receive a portion of any profits the plant makes, and you are paid back your initial investment after 10 years.***

On the following pages, different investment options for a renewable power plant in your municipality will be offered to you. We would like to know which option you would choose if these

⁵ Instructions highlighted in 'bold' were also seen highlighted in 'bold' by participants.

were your only options. Please make your choices as if you would likely make them in a real investment decision."

Participants were then asked to make a series of choice decisions between different investment projects which differed by the following attributes:

1. **Return on investment:** The amount of money you receive annually during the holding period as a share of your investment. For example, if the rate of return on capital is 10% and your investment is 1000 Euro, you receive 100 Euro per year. In addition, you receive your 1000 Euro at the end of the holding period (i.e. after 10 years). Return and initial investment will only be paid if the plant is not a total loss.
2. **Minimum investment requirement:** The smallest Euro amount that you need to invest to acquire a share in the renewable plant. Of course, you can invest more than the minimum investment requirement.
3. **Matching investment by municipality.** In some options, the municipality increases its investment in the plant in proportion to the amount of your investment.
4. **Risk of total loss.** There is a risk that your investment is permanently lost at any time during the holding period. For example, the economic conditions for the project may deteriorate, the project may be mismanaged, the technology may fail, the policy framework might change radically, or the project may get destroyed by an earthquake or a fire. Assume that there is no insurance to cover the financial losses associated with these events. For each option, the probability that this will happen is provided.
5. **Use of profits for nature conservation or support of low-income households:** 10% of the profits of the plant go to nature conservation measures in your municipality or are used to support low-income households in your municipality. Note that this has no impact on your return on investment. Remaining profits are reinvested in the plant.

The attributes and levels are shown in Table 2. In the survey for Poland, the monetary amounts used in the DCE were adjusted at the rate 1 EUR = 3 PLN to keep the relative value similar between countries in terms of purchasing power.

and Shupp, 2011). That is, participants were asked to make their choices as they would likely make them in a real investment decision. Second, our design included an opt-out option. That is, in addition to the two investment alternatives A and B shown in each choice task, participants could choose not to invest in either of the two alternatives.

To explore whether participants had understood key attributes of the DCE, the DCEs were followed by three comprehension questions with the response options a) true, b) false, and c) don't know.⁶ Participant who failed to provide correct responses had to re-read the instructions. Moreover, participants could read the explanations for each attribute again by moving their cursor over the attribute name in the choice sets.

Attributes and attribute levels were chosen so that investment options presented to respondents would be realistic thereby taking into consideration existing literature on DCEs on RECs. Our DCE also includes attributes of RECs which previous studies have not examined (matching by municipalities and the risk of total loss) or only scarcely examined (use of profits).

We use the **rate of return** to capture financial benefits of investments in RECs. The levels used are similar to those employed by Vuichard et al. (2019) and observed in cooperative investment projects in practice (e.g. IEA-RETD, 2016). Yet, they are substantially lower than in Cohen et al. (2021) who consider rates of return of up to 50%. The attribute levels **for minimum investment requirement** of 500 EUR and 1,000 EUR are similar to the reference investment levels in typical projects, while 100 EUR is below the minimum thresholds applied in practice (e.g. Cohen et al., 2021).

Extant literature has studied the role of **matching contributions by third parties** in public goods contexts such as charitable giving (e.g. Eckel and Grossman, 2003; Karlan and List, 2007; Meier, 2007, Epperson and Reif, 2019) and the willingness to offset travel-related CO₂-emissions (e.g. Kesternich et al., 2016; Schwirplies et al., 2019). Similarly, investment in a REC is an impure public good because it offers both private benefits such as returns on investment or lower electricity costs, and public benefits such as environmental, economic or social benefits for the local areas where the REC operates. Standard economic theory suggests that if individual investors only care about the total amount of funds the REC receives, matching by a third party decreases private investment in the REC ('crowding out'). In comparison, if individuals' investment in RECs is purely motivated by "warm glow" (Andreoni, 1989), they only care about the amount invested by themselves. In this case, matching has no effect on individuals' investment in RECs. Yet, experimental studies on the role of fairness preferences such as conditional cooperation typically find that individual spending on public goods increases if they observe, believe, or are informed

⁶ The three manipulation check statements were: 1) If the minimum investment amount is 500€, this means that you cannot invest less than 500€ (correct answer: true); 2) If the minimum investment amount is 500€, this means that you cannot invest more than 500€ (correct answer: false); 3) If the municipality matches your investment, this has no effect on your rate of return, i.e. the amount of money you receive annually during the holding period (correct answer: true). Shares of correct responses for question 1) were 81% in France, 84% in Germany, and 81% in Poland. Shares of correct responses for question 2) were 83% in France, 87% in Germany, and 81% in Poland. Shares of correct responses for question 3) were 43% in France, 52% in Germany, and 43% in Poland.

that others are willing to do the same (Fischbacher, Gächter and Fehr, 2001) ('crowding in'). Similarly, following the literature on motivational crowding (Nyborg and Rege, 2003; Frey and Stutzer, 2008), matching by third parties such as municipalities may evoke social responsibility and a sense of community, thus leading to a crowding in. For the matching we use a linear matching scheme. We limit the matching rate to 100% because findings by Karlan and List (2007) suggest that higher rates (of 200% and 300%) have no additional effect.

It proved difficult to obtain empirical data on **total losses of investment projects in decentralized electricity generation projects**. For wind turbines, fires caused by lightning are the major cause of total losses. Based on the data provided in Uidale et al. (2014), we estimated the probability of a total loss for a wind turbine within 10 years from fires alone at about 0.6 percent. According to Branner and Ghadirian (2014), annual failure rates for blades due to excessive loading or fatigue damage range between 0.06% and 0.29%. Hence, the figures chosen in our DCE seem generally plausible, even though the high end of the range may be above the rates of total losses observed in practice.

Our final attribute captures **co-benefits of projects in decentralized electricity generation for the municipality where the project is located**. Ek and Persson (2014) include as an attribute whether a share of the project revenue is transferred to the local community and earmarked for nature conservation measures or not. In our DCE we distinguished whether a share of the profits is used for nature conservation measures or to support low-income households in the respondents' municipality. Supporting low-income households may help mitigate the effects of increasing energy costs in the wake of the energy transition. For example, carbon taxes are typically regressive unless the revenues are redistributed (e.g. Feindt et al., 2021). This attribute also aligns investment options with existing EU regulation. Article 2 (16) of Directive 2018/2001 states that to benefit from the enabling framework for RECs (such as lower taxes for self-consumed electricity), their primary purpose must be to provide environmental, economic or social community benefits for its shareholders or members or for the local areas where it operates, rather than financial profits.

As a final point, we note that in contrast to, for example, Ek and Persson (2014), Lienhoop (2018) and Cohen et al. (2021) our DCE is **technology-neutral**. Similar to Knoefel et al. (2018) and Sagebiel et al. (2014), we decided not to include technology type such as wind turbines or solar photovoltaic plants neither in the framing to avoid confounding or distraction, nor as an attribute because the empirical literature on technology acceptance suggests that people typically prefer solar plants to other renewable technologies such as windmills or biomass (e.g. Kaenzig et al., 2013).

3.3 Individual-specific variables

To study the role of individual characteristics on investment decisions in renewable electricity generation projects, the DCE was followed by survey questions to elicit respondents' individual characteristics. This allows us to explore the role of individual preferences, capabilities, and social factors that have not or only scarcely been studied in the context of RECs such as risk aversion, loss aversion, financial literacy, reciprocity, place identity and motivational crowding.

Variables are described in detail below and a summary of the variables is presented in Table 3. All survey questions used to elicit the respondent-specific characteristics are presented in Table A1 in the Appendix.

Environmental preferences have previously been found to be positively related with intended investment in energy communities and RECs (e.g. Kalkbrenner and Rosen, 2016; Koirala et al., 2018; Cohen et al., 2021; Fischer et al., 2021). Similarly, several studies confirm that next to financial motives, environmental motives are most important for people to get engaged in energy communities (e.g. Seyfang et al., 2013; Sloot et al., 2019). In this study, environmental preferences are captured via **environmental identity**. To this end, respondents were asked to indicate on a five-point scale to what extent they agreed or disagreed with four statements adapted from Whitmarsh and O'Neill's (2010) environmental identity scale. Responses to the items were added up with higher values indicating stronger environmental identity, and a dummy variable, *highenvID*, was created that took on the value 1 if the respondent's score based on the four items was above the median score in their country, and 0 otherwise. We further asked respondents about their **most important investment criteria**. Respondents could select up to three criteria from a list of eleven criteria, including several financial criteria (financial return, financial risk, liquidity, ...), environmental criteria, social and/or ethical criteria and criteria relating to the type of products or services that the investment finances, the distribution of proceeds, and potential benefits to the local community. For respondents who selected environmental and/or social/ethical criteria as one of their top three investment criteria, the dummy variable *env_social_crit* was set to take on the value 1, and 0 otherwise.

Regarding economic preferences, we measured respondents' level of **risk aversion** by asking them to self-assess their general willingness to take risks on a five-point scale ranging from "completely unwilling to do so (1)", to "very willing to do so (5)". Using the same question but a ten-point scale, Dohmen et al. (2011) showed that self-assessed willingness to take risks is a reliable predictor of actual risk-taking behaviour in an incentivized lottery task, thereby confirming the behavioural validity of the survey measure. Based on the survey question, a dummy variable, *riskaverse*, was created that took on the value 1 if the respondent's self-assessed willingness to take risks was lower than the country median, and 0 otherwise.

Loss aversion was measured through six items selected from an 18-item loss aversion scale developed by De Baets and Buelens (2012). As in Blasch and Daminato (2020), the six items were selected because they capture respondents' dislike to deviate from a status quo rather than loss aversion more generally. Answers to the six items were summed up to form a loss aversion score. The dummy variable *lossaverse* was constructed which takes on the value 1 if the respondent's loss aversion score is above the median score in their country, and 0 otherwise.

To assess respondents' **financial literacy**, we used three questions that were originally designed by Lusardi and Mitchell (2011) and address respondents' understanding of interest rates, inflation rates, and risk and financial diversification. These scales have also been used by Fischer et al. (2021) and Gutsche et al. (2021). For each respondent we counted the number of correct responses to the three questions. We then set the dummy variable *lowfinlit* to take on the value 1 if the respondent's number of correct responses was below the country median, and 0 otherwise. In addition, to capture respondents' **experience with sustainable investments**, we asked

respondents if they had ever invested in sustainable investment assets, renewable energy cooperatives or sustainable crowdfunding projects. If the respondent answered “Yes” to any of the three questions, the dummy variable *sust_invest* was set to take on the value 1, and 0 otherwise.

Looking at social factors with a potential impact on investment decisions, we adapted three questions from Whitmarsh and O’Neill (2010) to measure respondents’ **subjective social norms** regarding sustainable investments:⁷ 1) *Do any of your family members, friends or colleagues invest in sustainable financial investments?* (Response options: Yes; No; Don’t know); 2) *How much influence do your family, friends and colleagues have on your decision to invest – or not invest– in sustainable investments?* (Five-point scale ranging from no influence (1) to large influence (5)); 3) *In general, what do you think your family’s, friends’ or colleagues’ views would be of you investing in sustainable investments?* (Five-point scale from very unfavourable (1) to very favourable (5)). Based on these three questions we constructed a score that increased by 1 if respondents replied “Yes” to the first question, and if respondents chose a scale point above the country median in the second and third question. Finally, we classified respondents as showing high social norms and set the dummy variable *social_norms* equal to 1 if respondents’ overall score was above the median score in their respective country.

To measure respondents’ **positive reciprocity**, we used one item from the positive reciprocity scale developed by Perugini et al. (2003): *“If someone does me a favour, I am ready to return it.”* Selected items from Perugini et al.’s scale, including the item we use, have also been employed, for example, by Dohmen et al. (2009), Fischer et al. (2021), and Ziegler (2021). Respondents were asked to provide an answer on a five-point scale anchored by strongly disagree (1) and strongly agree (5). A dummy variable, *pos_reciprocity*, was then created, taking on the value 1 if the respondent’s answer on the five-point scale was above or equal to the country median, and 0 otherwise.

Respondents’ **place identity** was measured using a score based on four questions capturing respondents’ subjective identification with their city, community or region, their participation in the local community life on different levels (i. e. through participation in local elections, membership in local clubs or associations or the location of respondents’ workplace), and their length of residency. The score ranges from 0 to 4, where 4 indicates that the respondent’s stated identification with her city, community, or region on a five-point scale is above the country median, that she voted in the last local election, that she participates in clubs or associations or works within her municipality, and that she has been living in her municipality for at least 10 years. Based on the score, the dummy variable *highplaceID* was constructed to take on the value 1 if the respondent’s score was above the median score, and 0 otherwise.

To capture potential **crowding effects** of government-level policies on respondents’ intended investment in RECs, we asked respondents to indicate their level of agreement with the following

⁷ Whitmarsh and O’Neill (2010) measured subjective social norms regarding the purchase of carbon offsets. We reformulated the three items to match the investment decisions in our DCE and used 5-point rather than 4-point scales.

statement on a five-point scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5): “If you think about how the sustainable energy transition is being implemented, how satisfied are you with the current performance of the [French/German/Polish] government?” A similar item has been used in the German “Social Sustainability Barometer for the Energiewende” (Wolf, 2020). The dummy variable *unsatisfied* was coded to take on the value 1 if the level of agreement with the statement was below the median level in the respective country, and 0 otherwise.

Finally, based on the screening questions and an additional question on respondents’ level of education, a set of dummy variables was created taking on the value 1 if respondents were, respectively, female (*female*), below the age of 35 (*below35*), above the age of 65 (*above64*), in their country's lowest income category (*lowincome*), in their country's highest income category (*highincome*), or holding a higher education degree (*higheduc*), and 0 otherwise. We included these **socio-demographic variables** as control variables to mitigate potential omitted variable bias in our analysis.

Table 3: Individual-specific variables

Variable	Description	% of observations with variable equal to 1		
		France	Germany	Poland
<i>highenvID</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's score on a four-item environmental identity Likert scale is above the country median, 0 otherwise.	51.8	47.5	46.3
<i>env_social_crit</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent ranks environmental and/or social/ethical criteria among her top three investment criteria, 0 otherwise.	19.6	28.7	16.0
<i>riskaverse</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's self-declared willingness to take risks is below the country median, 0 otherwise.	38.2	40.6	29.1
<i>lossaverse</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's score on a six-item loss aversion Likert scale is below the country median, 0 otherwise.	38.9	42.9	42.4
<i>lowfinlit</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's number of correct responses to three financial literacy questions is below the country median, 0 otherwise.	42.1	21.0	39.7
<i>sust_invest</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent has previously invested in sustainable investment assets or crowdfunding projects or in renewable energy cooperatives, 0 otherwise.	15.4	17.7	6.0
<i>social_norms</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's perception of social pressure to participate in sustainable financial investments (measured using three	33.6	44.5	36.8

Variable	Description	% of observations with variable equal to 1		
		France	Germany	Poland
	items) is above the country median, 0 otherwise			
<i>pos_reciprocity</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's self-declared willingness to return favours is above the country median, 0 otherwise.	56.8	84.8	84.2
<i>highplaceID</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's integration with her local community (measured using four questions) is above the country median, 0 otherwise.	33.8	23.5	19.8
<i>unsatisfied</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's satisfaction with their national government's implementation of the sustainable energy transition is below the country median, 0 otherwise.	23.8	23.7	41.3
<i>female</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent is female, 0 otherwise.	50.1	51.0	51.9
<i>below35</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent is below the age of 35, 0 otherwise.	17.2	24.3	25.7
<i>above64</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent is above the age of 64, 0 otherwise.	26.4	23.6	18.6
<i>lowincome</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's monthly household income after tax is below 2,000 EUR (FR, DE), or below 3,000 PLN (PL), 0 otherwise.	38.6	31.6	24.7
<i>highincome</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's monthly household income after tax is above 4,000 EUR (FR), above 3,600 EUR (DE), or above 5,900 PLN (PL), 0 otherwise.	20.7	40.1	33.9
<i>higheduc</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent holds a higher education degree, 0 otherwise.	50.4	35.0	46.7

3.4 Results

In this section, we present and discuss the results of the fixed-effects logit model. To allow for a meaningful interpretation Table 4 reports the estimated average discrete and marginal effects, i.e., the change in the average probability that a respondent chooses investment option A or B over the opt-out option in response to a one-unit increase in the referenced variable. On average, respondents chose the opt-out option over either investment option A or investment option B in 24% of cases in France and Germany and in 26% of cases in Poland. In the three countries

combined, about 89% of respondents chose to invest in at least one of the 16 investment options shown to them in eight choice sets. The respective shares are 89% for France, 90% for Germany, and 88% for Poland. Thus, in general respondents appear to have a high interest in the RECs shown in our DCE, with only small differences across countries.

Table A2 in the Appendix shows the parameter estimates of the latent utility function in equation (1). We first present the findings for the attributes of the DCE and then for the variables reflecting preferences, capabilities, and social factors. Finally, we briefly describe our findings on socio-demographic factors.

Table 4: Estimated average discrete and marginal effects of attribute and respondent-specific variables on the probability of choosing an investment option over the opt-out option

	France		Germany		Poland	
	marginal effect	p-value	marginal effect	p-value	marginal effect	p-value
Attributes						
<i>rate</i>	0.023***	0.000	0.034***	0.000	0.014***	0.000
<i>min_medium</i>	-0.033***	0.001	-0.026**	0.010	-0.015	0.173
<i>min_high</i>	-0.080***	0.000	-0.065***	0.000	-0.027***	0.009
<i>match_half</i>	0.017**	0.030	0.024***	0.003	0.013	0.104
<i>match_full</i>	0.012	0.137	0.061***	0.000	0.009	0.290
<i>loss</i>	-0.049***	0.000	-0.049***	0.000	-0.038***	0.000
<i>nature</i>	0.031***	0.000	0.020**	0.037	0.013	0.136
Individual-specific variables						
<i>highenvID</i>	0.063**	0.016	0.033	0.213	0.047	0.103
<i>env_social_crit</i>	0.124***	0.000	0.132***	0.000	0.118***	0.001
<i>riskaverse</i>	-0.092***	0.000	-0.068***	0.009	-0.062**	0.035
<i>lossaverse</i>	-0.014	0.576	0.032	0.199	-0.014	0.599
<i>lowfinlit</i>	-0.113***	0.000	-0.120***	0.000	-0.141***	0.000
<i>sust_invest</i>	0.103***	0.005	0.099***	0.003	0.189***	0.003
<i>social_norms</i>	0.147***	0.000	0.125***	0.000	0.080***	0.006
<i>pos_reciprocity</i>	0.041	0.104	0.117***	0.001	0.065*	0.077
<i>highplaceID</i>	0.098***	0.000	0.012	0.665	0.087***	0.009
<i>unsatisfied</i>	-0.021	0.471	-0.058**	0.041	-0.010	0.720
<i>female</i>	-0.031	0.232	-0.024	0.334	-0.035	0.207
<i>below35</i>	0.105***	0.001	0.029	0.320	0.135***	0.000
<i>above64</i>	-0.045*	0.098	-0.082***	0.009	-0.136***	0.000
<i>lowincome</i>	-0.028	0.297	-0.071**	0.028	-0.016	0.638
<i>highincome</i>	0.071**	0.042	-0.028	0.358	0.068**	0.028
<i>higheduc</i>	-0.028	0.270	-0.024	0.373	-0.027	0.318
Number of respondents	1,074		986		936	
Number of observations	21,328		19,606		18,700	

*** p-value < 0.01, ** p-value < 0.05, * p-value < 0.1

3.4.1 Attributes

As expected and consistent with previous literature (e.g. Vuichard et al., 2019; Pons-Seres de Brauwer and Cohen, 2020; Cohen et al., 2021) respondents in all three countries prefer projects with higher **rates of return**. More specifically, the point estimate of the marginal effect suggests that an increase in the rate of return by one percentage point increases the probability of choosing investment option A or B over the opt-out response by about 2.3 percentage points in France, 3.4 percentage points in Germany, and 1.4 percentage points in Poland. To discuss the findings for the other attributes, we estimate the marginal willingness to pay (WTP) in terms of the change in the rate of return in response to a one-unit changes in the attribute levels. Thus, our WTP measure reflects participant willingness to trade-off rate of return against other attributes in the DCE. Following equation (2), the marginal WTP is estimated as $\frac{-\beta_k}{\beta_r}$ where β_r is the estimated coefficient associated with the rate of return, and β_k is the estimated coefficient associated with attribute k (as reported in Table A2). Table 5 shows the WTP estimates together with the 95% confidence interval assuming asymptotic normality of $\frac{-\beta_k}{\beta_r}$.

The findings for *min_low* and *min_medium* imply that on average, respondents prefer lower to higher **minimum investment requirements**. High minimum investment requirements have previously been identified as a barrier to invest in renewable energy cooperatives in DCEs (e.g. Cohen et al., 2021). Reasons include capital constraints, in particular in low-income households (Lowitzsch, 2019). Similarly, higher stakes involve higher financial risks and potential losses. Our WTP estimates suggest that if the minimum investment requirement was 500 EUR (1000 EUR) instead of 100 EUR, respondents would be willing to give up 1.40 (3.39) percentage points of return in France, 0.75 (1.89) percentage points of return in Germany, and 1.09 (1.96) percentage points of return in Poland.

On average, respondents in France and Germany prefer a **matching** of their investment by the municipality. The coefficient associated with full matching in France is not statistically significant at the 10% level. However, estimating the model with a single dummy variable for matching (equal to 1 if the investment is matched – full or half – and 0 otherwise) shows that matching is preferred to no matching and that the effect is statistically significant at the 5% level. This finding is in line with the empirical literature on the role of matching in other contexts (e.g. Eckel and Grossman, 2003; Karlan and List, 2007; Meier, 2007; Kesternich et al., 2016; Schwirplies et al., 2019). For Germany, full matching is preferred to half matching⁸, while for France we find no evidence that the difference between both types of matching is statistically significant.⁹ In Poland, on average, no statistically significant preference for matching is revealed, though the coefficient associated with half matching is just shy of being statistically significant at the 10% level.

⁸ A Wald test for equality of the coefficients for *match_half* and *match_full* shows that a 100% matching is preferred to a 50% matching ($p < 0.001$).

⁹ A Wald test for equality of the coefficients for *match_half* and *match_full* shows no statistically significant difference between the coefficients ($p = 0.45$).

As can be seen from Table 5, respondents in Germany, for example, would be willing to give up about 0.70 (1.81) percentage points in return if their investment in the project was half matched (fully matched) rather than not matched.

On average, respondents in all three countries dislike higher **chances of losing their entire investment**. According to the WTP estimates, the average participant in France is willing to give up about 2 percentage points of return for a 1 percentage point decrease in the risk to experience a total loss. This figure is lower in Germany and higher in Poland than in France. Hence, respondents in all three countries, yet particularly in Poland, appear to respond strongly to the risk of losing the entire investment, possibly because of high risk and loss aversion.

Finally, we find that respondents in all three countries prefer **profits to be used for nature conservation measures** in respondents' municipality rather than for the support of low-income households in their municipality, although the coefficient for Poland is just shy of being statistically significant at conventional levels of significance. In general, this result is consistent with Ek and Persson (2014) in a similar context. This finding may be explained by self-interest because on average respondents may expect to benefit directly from the amenities of local environmental protection measures. In contrast, only low-income households would benefit from dedicating the profits to fund low-income households. On average, respondents from France are willing to give up 1.32 percentage points in returns if profits are used to fund nature conservation measures rather than low-income households in their municipality. For Poland, and in particular Germany, this figure is lower than for France.

Table 5: Estimated WTP for attributes in terms of rate of return

Attribute	Estimated WTP	95% confidence interval	
		Lower limit	Upper limit
France			
<i>min_medium</i>	-1.40	-2.34	-0.47
<i>min_high</i>	-3.39	-4.37	-2.41
<i>match_half</i>	0.73	0.07	1.39
<i>match_full</i>	0.50	-0.12	1.13
<i>loss</i>	-2.10	-2.53	-1.69
<i>nature</i>	1.32	0.68	1.96
Germany			
<i>min_medium</i>	-0.75	-1.36	-0.14
<i>min_high</i>	-1.89	-2.45	-1.28
<i>match_half</i>	0.70	0.24	1.16
<i>match_full</i>	1.81	1.32	2.29
<i>loss</i>	-1.43	-1.65	-1.22
<i>nature</i>	0.58	0.07	1.09
Poland			
<i>min_medium</i>	-1.09	-2.82	0.63
<i>min_high</i>	-1.96	-3.47	-0.46
<i>match_half</i>	0.97	-0.21	2.14
<i>match_full</i>	0.63	-0.46	1.72
<i>loss</i>	-2.72	-3.66	-1.79
<i>nature</i>	0.96	-0.21	2.12

3.4.2 Individual-specific variables

First, our findings on the role of preferences suggest that respondents with an above-median score of **environmental identity** in their country are more likely to invest in projects shown in the DCE than to choose the opt-out option. On average, the effect size of *highenvID* is 6.3 percentage points for France, 3.3 percentage points for Germany, and 4.7 percentage points for Poland. Because investments in decentralized renewable electricity generation typically lower greenhouse gas and other emissions, this finding is not surprising and in line with the empirical literature analysing investments in RECs/energy communities (e.g. Kalkbrenner and Rosen, 2016; Koirala et al., 2018; Cohen et al., 2021; Fischer et al., 2021). Similarly, we find that respondents who rank environmental and/or social/ethical criteria among their **top three investment criteria** are more likely to invest in a REC than to opt out. The effect size of 12.4 percentage points for France, 13.2 percentage points for Germany, and 11.8 percentage points for Poland confirms that these motives play a significant role in people's decision to invest in renewable electricity generation projects in all three countries.

Further, for all three countries we find that respondents with a below-median **willingness to take risks** in their country are less likely to choose a project in our DCE than to opt out. This finding differs from Fischer et al. (2021), who fail to find a statistically significant relation between risk aversion and intended investment in RECs, but is in line with the thrust of the substantial literature studying the role of risk aversion on financial investments in general (e.g. Barbers and Thaler, 2005, Falk et al., 2018) and the scant literature exploring the role of risk aversion on sustainable financial investments (Gutsche et al., 2021). Because the decision to invest in decentralized renewable electricity generation involves uncertainty, risk preferences are expected to matter. More specifically, risk aversion is expected to impede investments in these projects because profits depend on uncertain factors such as weather conditions (e.g. wind speeds, solar radiation), future electricity prices, technology performance and reliability, or future regulations. Arguably, we find risk aversion to be correlated with participants' investment choices because our DCE includes the possibility of a total loss as an attribute. Finally, we note that the effect size associated with risk aversion ranges between -9.2 percentage points for France and -6.8 and -6.2 percentage points in Germany and Poland.

Contrary to our expectation, for all three countries we fail to find a statistically significant relation of **loss aversion** and respondents' intention to invest in a renewable electricity generation project shown in our DCE. A possible explanation for this no result could be that loss-averse respondents react more strongly negatively to the probability of a total loss, but at the same time are also more reluctant to forgo high rates of return or matching by the government. Thus, the effects of loss aversion on investment decisions in our DCE could on average cancel out.

Next, our findings on the role of capabilities suggest that in all three countries respondents with an above-median score of **financial literacy** in the country sample are more likely to choose a REC than the opt-out option. This finding is similar to the scant literature using a similar score to analyse the relation between financial literacy and investment in RECs (Fischer, 2021) and in sustainable financial investments (Gutsche et al., 2021). Likewise, and similar to Fischer et al. (2021), for all three countries we find that respondents who **previously invested** in sustainable

investment assets or crowdfunding projects or in renewable energy cooperatives are more likely to select an investment option than to opt out.

Looking at social factors, we first observe that in all three countries **social norms** are positively related with the probability that an investment option is chosen. This confirms findings of earlier work on the role of social norms by Kalkbrenner and Roosen (2016) and Fischer et al. (2021) in the context of RECs and by Riedl and Smeets (2017) and Gutsche et al. (2019) in the context of sustainable financial investments. More specifically, in France, respondents whose perception of social pressure to participate in sustainable financial investments is above the country median are 14.7 percentage points less likely to choose the opt-out option. The corresponding figures are 11.7 percentage points for France, and 8 percentage points for Poland. Thus, the effect size also appears to be quite large, in particular in France. Next, our results suggest that in all three countries **reciprocity preferences** measured by respondent's self-declared willingness to return favours are positively related with the probability that respondents choose an investment option. For France, however, the coefficient is just shy of being statistically significant at conventional levels ($p=0.104$). We also note that the effect size varies markedly across countries, ranging from 4.1 percentage points in France to 6.5 percentage points in Poland, and 11.7 percentage points in Germany. Arguably, this finding may be explained by the fact that the DCE includes as an attribute matching by municipalities. In a related context, Fischer et al. (2021) find that intended investment in RECs is positively related with negative reciprocity and with positive reciprocity, but the association with positive reciprocity is not statistically significant. We further find that in all three countries place identity is positively associated with respondents' propensity to choose a REC investment, but for the sample from Germany, the coefficient is far from being statistically significant. Respondents with an above-median score on our **place identity** index in France (Poland) are found to have a 9.8 (8.7) percentage points higher probability to invest in the options shown in the DCE than participants with a below-median score, suggesting that place identity is a relevant predictor of stated investments in France and Poland.

Finally, we find that in Germany respondents who are **unsatisfied** with their national government's implementation of the sustainable energy transition are less likely to choose a REC investment option. For France and Poland, the coefficient is far from being statistically significant. The finding for Germany is consistent with the literature on motivational crowding (Nyborg and Rege, 2003; Frey and Stutzer, 2008) and suggests that government policy promoting the energy transition are likely to spur investments in decentralized renewable electricity projects. The effect size of 5.8 percentage points further implies that government policy in Germany may have meaningful crowding-in effects.

These findings on the role of preferences, capabilities and social factors are derived while controlling for **socio-demographic characteristics** to mitigate potential omitted variable bias. According to Table 4, women are less likely to choose an investment in a renewable electricity generation project than men, but the coefficient is not statistically significant in any of the country samples. In comparison, in all three countries we find that participants who are older than 64 years are less likely to invest in such a project than younger participants. Similarly, our results for France and Poland (but not for Germany) suggest that participants who are younger than 35 years are more likely to choose an investment in a decentralized renewable electricity project. The relation of such an investment with age appears to be particularly strong in Poland.

Our findings on income show that in each country, higher income households tend to be more likely to choose an investment option over the opt-out option compared to lower-income households. More precisely, for France and Poland, we find that high-income participants are more likely to opt for an investment option. In Germany, low-income households are more likely to choose the opt-out option. Finally, we fail to find a relation between education and participant propensity to choose an investment option shown in the DCE.

4 DISCRETE CHOICE EXPERIMENT ON PARTICIPATION IN RENEWABLE ENERGY COOPERATIVES (FRANCE)

In this section, we present and analyse this DCE on participation in RECs. We are particularly interested in participant valuation of characteristics that would facilitate commercial investors' engagement in such projects and thus providing capital necessary to finance the energy transition in France.

We organize this section as follows. First, we provide more details on the sample. Then we describe the DCE design and report and discuss the results.

4.1 Sample

In France, 1,022 participants completed the DCE on participation in RECs. Summary statistics for the sample are presented in Table 6 next to national population statistics for comparison. Overall, sample statistics are close to national statistics, though participants below the age of 30 are slightly underrepresented.

Table 6: Sample characteristics for participants in the DCE on participation in renewable energy cooperatives

	Sample	Population
Share of males^a	49.8%	48.3%
Age (share of adult population)^b		
18-29	13.9%	17.6%
30-49	33.3%	32.3%
50-64	25.8%	24.5%
65 and older	27.0%	25.5%
Household income		
2,000 EUR or less ^c	37.2%	36%
2,001 – 4,000 EUR	40.4%	42%
More than 4,000 EUR	22.4%	23%

^a Source of population statistics: Eurostat (2020). ^b Source of population statistics: Eurostat (2019). ^c Source of population statistics: Insee (2017).

4.2 Discrete choice experiment design

To introduce the DCE on investments in RECs, we used the following framing:¹⁰

¹⁰ Instructions highlighted in 'bold' were also seen highlighted in 'bold' by participants.

"In this part of the survey, we invite you to make a series of hypothetical choices between different investment opportunities in renewable energy cooperatives. There are no right or wrong answers to these questions.

Renewable energy cooperatives (RECs) are organizations that own or operate renewable energy plants such as solar power plants, wind farms or biogas plants. They are controlled by their members or shareholders who finance investments in the renewable energy projects. Members are other private citizens and, in some cases, also municipalities and local private enterprises.

*Imagine you are being offered the opportunity to **become a member and invest in a renewable energy cooperative (REC) in your municipality**. The REC sells carbon-free electricity into the electricity grid and makes money over time. If you invest in the REC, you annually receive a portion of any profits the REC makes. Your membership ends after 10 years and you are paid back your initial investment. The smallest Euro amount that you need to invest to acquire a share in the renewable plant is 100 Euro. Of course, you can invest more. As a member, you will also gain voting rights to participate in the decision-making of the REC (e.g. to decide in which activities funds should be invested). On the following pages, different RECs will be presented to you. We would like to know in which REC you would invest if these were your only options. You may assume that all RECs are located within your municipality and produce electricity using your preferred technology (e.g. using solar plants, wind farms, biogas, ...). Please make your choices as if you would likely make them in a real investment decision.*

Participants were then asked to make a series of choice decisions between different investment projects which differed by the following attributes:

- 1. Type of members:** Some RECs allow only citizens to become members and invest. Other RECs also allow the local municipality or local private enterprises to become members.
- 2. Voting rights:** In some RECs, each member has one vote and can participate equally in the REC's governance. In other RECs, the voting rights are based on the capital contribution. This means that members who invest more have more influence on the REC's governance compared to members who invest less. However, citizens and the local municipality always hold more voting rights than private enterprises, no matter how much private enterprises invest.
- 3. Delegation of voting rights to a proxy:** In some RECs presented to you, citizens do not have to participate in the REC's governance themselves but can delegate their voting rights to a proxy who will then represent them. In other RECs, citizens must participate in the REC's governance themselves and cannot delegate their voting rights.
- 4. Return on investment:** The amount of money you receive annually during the holding period as a share of your investment. For example, if the rate of return on capital is 10% and your investment is 1000 Euro, you receive 100 Euro per year. In addition, you receive your 1000 Euro at the end of the holding period (i.e. after 10 years). Return and initial investment will only be paid if the plant is not a total loss.
- 5. Self-consumption:** Some RECs sell electricity directly to their members. If you become a member and invest in one of the RECs presented to you, you can purchase 0%, 35%, or 70% of

the electricity your household uses directly from this REC. The electricity cost to your household remains unchanged (i.e. electricity cost is the same as under your current electricity contract).

The attributes and levels are shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Levels of different attributes considered in the DCE on participation in renewable energy cooperatives

Attribute	Levels	Variable	Type
Type of members	Citizens only, citizens and municipality, citizens, municipality and local private enterprises;	(baseline) <i>municipality</i> <i>firms</i>	dummy dummy
Voting rights	one member one vote, based on capital;	(baseline) <i>capital_cont</i>	dummy
Delegation of voting rights to a proxy	possible, not possible;	<i>delegation</i> (baseline)	dummy
Return on investment	1%, 3%, 4%, 5%, 7%;	<i>rate</i>	continuous
Self-consumption	0%, 35%, 70%;	(baseline) <i>self35</i> <i>self70</i>	dummy dummy

As in the previously described DCE, we employed a Bayesian-efficient design (Sándor and Wedel, 2001) using the NGENE software (ChoiceMetrics, 2014) and relying on priors obtained from a pre-test with 50 participants. Our final design consisted of 24 choice sets with two alternatives each, divided into three blocks. Participants in the DCE were randomly assigned to one block and thus saw eight choice sets each.

Figure 2 shows an example of a choice set used in the DCE.

To mitigate hypothetical bias and as described in the previous DCE, we included 'cheap talk' and an opt-out option (see Figure 2). We also included three comprehension questions with response options: a) true, b) false, and c) don't know.¹¹ Participant who failed to provide correct responses had to re-read the instructions. Moreover, participants could read the explanations for each attribute again by moving their cursor over the attribute name in the choice sets.

¹¹ The three manipulation check statements were: 1) If voting rights are based on capital contribution, members who invest more have more influence on the REC's governance compared to members who invest less (correct answer: true); 2) Private enterprises can hold more voting rights than citizens and the local municipality (correct answer: false); 3) Purchasing electricity from the REC has no impact on your household's electricity costs (correct answer: true). The shares of correct responses were 50%, 41% and 37% for questions 1, 2 and 3, respectively, highlighting the importance of the manipulation check and the necessity for participants to reread the instructions.

In which of the following renewable energy cooperatives would you like to invest?

Please consider thoroughly how this investment will affect your budget, and that you actually are willing to invest at least 100€ in the alternative that you choose.

	Cooperative A	Cooperative B
Type of members	citizens only	citizens and municipality
Voting rights	based on capital contribution	one member one vote
Delegation of voting rights to a proxy	possible	not possible
Return on investment	7%	3%
Self-consumption	35%	70%

	Cooperative A	Cooperative B	None of these cooperatives
I would like to become a member and invest 100€ or more in:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure 2: Example of a choice set in the DCE on participation in renewable energy cooperatives

Our choice of attributes and attribute levels was guided by the literature studying individual motives to join bottom-up sustainable energy initiatives (e.g. Sloot et al., 2019) and the literature employing DCE models in related contexts. In particular, the attributes are assumed to reflect the challenges and potential trade-offs for RECs to include municipalities and/or commercial investors to accelerate the diffusion and scale of RECs while retaining the incentives and benefits of individual consumer participation. Finally, the attributes reflect criteria which RECs must satisfy according to the recast of the Renewable Energy Directive 2018/2001 (RED II) to benefit from an 'enabling framework' for RECs specified by individual member states. Pursuant to Article 2 (16) of Directive 2018/2001 these criteria pertain to eligibility (shareholders or members are natural persons, small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) or local authorities, including municipalities), ownership and control (must effectively be controlled by shareholders or members that are located in the proximity of the project, i.e. 51% of shares must be owned by these actors; must be autonomous, i.e. no individual shareholder must own more than 33% of the stock), the primary purpose (must provide environmental, economic or social community benefits for its shareholders or members or for the local areas where it operates, rather than financial profits), and membership (non-discriminatory voluntary participation open to all potential local members) (see also Hoicka et al., 2021).

Against this background, the attribute '**type of membership**' reflects the provisions of RED II and distinguishes between three types of membership structures. That is, shares of the REC may be owned by citizens only (baseline), by citizens and the municipality, or by citizens, the municipality and local private enterprises. Previous research in related contexts suggests that citizens may

dislike involvement of commercial investors in decision-making (Ek and Persson, 2014; Brennan and Rensburg, 2020; Cohen et al., 2021).

There are various governance models which enable citizens' participation in renewables projects. The cooperative governance model has been the most popular legal structure for small-scale RECs in Europe in the past (e.g. Caramizaru and Uihlein, 2020). This model entails the **'one-member, one vote' principle** regardless of the share of stock owned by a member. Yet, this principle may scare off (local) commercial investors because their representation in supervisory bodies and their impact on management decisions would not adequately reflect their financial involvement (e.g. Hoicka et al., 2021). Therefore, in our DCE we also allowed voting rights to be proportional to the shareholding, similar to Sagebiel et al. (2014). In this case, to be in line with RED II regulation, citizens and the local municipality were assumed to hold the majority of voting rights.

Under the cooperative governance model, the general assembly is the highest decision-making body. A certain number of voting rights must be represented at the general assembly in order for the body to have a quorum. The possibility to participate at these meetings and to be actively involved in the governance of RECs may be important for citizen shareholders to join a REC (see SONNET Deliverable D3.2). At the same time, preparing and participating at these meetings involves transaction costs. We therefore also included the **possibility to delegate voting rights to a proxy** as an attribute.

Owning shares in RECs leads to **financial benefits**. Following Vuichard et al. (2019), Pons-Seres de Brauwer and Cohen (2020), and Cohen et al. (2021), we assumed that shareholders receive an annual return on their investment. The levels used in our DCE are similar to those used by Vuichard et al. (2019) and observed in cooperative investment projects in practice (e.g. IEA-RETD, 2016).

The EU Clean Energy Package legal framework of regulation (EU) 2018/1999 allows RECs to **share electricity between members and shareholders**, even when this involves using the public grid. Our final attribute captures this option, varying the share of their electricity consumption participants may purchase directly from the REC. A recent survey of the adult population in France suggests that 68% of the respondents would be interested in producing and using their own energy (from photovoltaic plants), even if it was a bit more expensive, 31% of the respondents would like to produce enough electricity to be autonomous. Similarly, 51% of the respondents stated that becoming energy autonomous would be a reason to generate electricity at home. Only energy cost savings appeared to be more important than energy autonomy (ADEME and Opinion Way, 2019).

Because we are primarily interested in the socio-psychological aspects of self-consumption and to avoid confounding of this attribute with the attribute reflecting financial benefits (i.e. rate of return), we assumed that the electricity cost to the household does not vary with the share of electricity self-consumed. Indeed, for many prosumers self-consumption appears to be driven by non-financial motives such as the motive for autonomy mentioned earlier. Similarly, Gautier et al. (2019) find that about 40% of owners of residential photovoltaic modules self-consume electricity when there are no financial incentives to do so. In particular, they find that prosumers with high

environmental motives are more prone to adapt their electricity consumption to help synchronize household electricity consumption and production.

Finally, we want to point out that the DCE on participation in RECs is **technology-neutral**, similar to the DCE on investment projects in decentralized renewable electricity generation described in section 3.

4.3 Individual-specific variables¹²

To study the role of individual characteristics on investment decisions in RECs, the DCE was followed by survey questions eliciting respondents' environmental and economic preferences, capabilities, and social factors. This allows us to explore the role of factors that have not or only scarcely been studied in the context of RECs or energy communities such as risk aversion, financial literacy, reciprocity, place identity and motivational crowding.

Variables are described in detail below and a summary of the variables is presented in 8. All survey questions used to elicit the respondent-specific characteristics are presented in Table A1 in the Appendix.

Environmental preferences have previously been found to be positively related with intended investment in energy communities and RECs (e.g. Kalkbrenner and Rosen, 2016; Koirala et al., 2018; Cohen et al., 2021; Fischer et al., 2021). Similarly, several studies confirm that next to financial motives, environmental motives are most important for people to get engaged in energy communities (e.g. Seyfang et al., 2013; Sloot et al., 2019). In this study, environmental preferences are captured via **environmental identity**. To this end, respondents were asked to indicate on a five-point scale to what extent they agreed or disagreed with four statements adapted from Whitmarsh and O'Neill's (2010) environmental identity scale. Responses to the items were added up with higher values indicating stronger environmental identity, and a dummy variable, *highenvID*, was created that took on the value 1 if the respondent's score based on the four items was above the median score, and 0 otherwise. We further asked respondents about their **most important investment criteria**. Respondents could select up to three criteria from a list of eleven criteria, including several financial criteria (financial return, financial risks, liquidity, ...), environmental criteria, social and/or ethical criteria and criteria relating to the type of products or services that the investment finances, the distribution of proceeds, and potential benefits to the local community. For respondents who selected environmental and/or social/ethical criteria as one of their top three investment criteria, the dummy variable *env_social_crit* was set to take on the value 1, and 0 otherwise.

Regarding economic preferences, we measured respondents' **level of risk aversion** by asking them to self-assess their general willingness to take risks on a five-point scale ranging from

¹² This section is largely identical to section 2.3. By repeating the description of the individual-specific variables, section 3 can be read and understood independently of section 2.

“completely unwilling to do so (1)”, to “very willing to do so (5)”. Using the same question but a ten-point scale, Dohmen et al. (2011) showed that self-assessed willingness to take risks is a reliable predictor of actual risk-taking behaviour in an incentivized lottery task, thereby confirming the behavioural validity of the survey measure. Based on the survey question, a dummy variable, *riskaverse*, was created that took on the value 1 if the respondent’s self-assessed willingness to take risks was lower than the median, and 0 otherwise.

To assess respondents’ **financial literacy**, we used three questions that were originally designed by Lusardi and Mitchell (2011) and address respondents’ understanding of interest rates, inflation rates, and risk and financial diversification. These scales have also been used by Fischer et al. (2021) and Gutsche et al. (2021). For each respondent we counted the number of correct responses to the three questions. We then constructed the dummy variable *lowfinlit* which takes on the value 1 if the respondent’s number of correct responses is below the median, and 0 otherwise. In addition, to capture respondents’ **experience with sustainable investments**, we asked respondents if they had ever invested in sustainable investment assets, renewable energy cooperatives or sustainable crowdfunding projects. If the respondent answered “Yes” to any of the three questions, the dummy variable *sust_invest* was set to take on the value 1, and 0 otherwise.

Looking at social factors with a potential impact on investment decisions, we adapted three questions from Whitmarsh and O’Neill (2010) to measure respondents’ **subjective social norms** regarding sustainable investments:¹³ 1) *Do any of your family members, friends or colleagues invest in sustainable financial investments?* (Response options: Yes; No; Don’t know); 2) *How much influence do your family, friends and colleagues have on your decision to invest – or not invest– in sustainable investments?* (Five-point scale ranging from no influence (1) to large influence (5)); 3) *In general, what do you think your family’s, friends’ or colleagues’ views would be of you investing in sustainable investments?* (Five-point scale from very unfavourable (1) to very favourable (5)). Based on these three questions we constructed a score that increased by 1 if respondents replied “Yes” to the first question, and if respondents chose a scale point above the median in the second and third question. Finally, we classified respondents as showing high social norms and set the dummy variable *social_norms* equal to 1 if respondents’ overall score was above the median score.

To measure respondents’ **positive reciprocity**, we used one item from the positive reciprocity scale developed by Perugini et al. (2003): *“If someone does me a favour, I am ready to return it.”* Selected items from Perugini et al.’s scale, including the item we use, have also been employed, for example, by Dohmen et al. (2009), Fischer et al. (2021), and Ziegler (2021). Respondents were asked to provide an answer on a five-point scale anchored by strongly disagree (1) and strongly agree (5). A dummy variable, *pos_reciprocity*, was then created, taking on the value 1 if the respondent’s answer on the five-point scale was above or equal to the median, and 0 otherwise.

¹³ Whitmarsh and O’Neill (2010) measured subjective social norms regarding the purchase of carbon offsets. We reformulated the three items to match the investment decisions in our DCE and used 5-point rather than 4-point scales.

Respondents' **place identity** was measured using a score based on four questions capturing respondents' subjective identification with their city, community or region, their participation in the local community life on different levels (i.e. through participation in local elections, membership in local clubs or associations or the location of respondents' workplace), and their length of residency. The score ranges from 0 to 4, where 4 indicates that the respondent's stated identification with her city, community or region on a five-point scale is above the median, that she voted in the last local election, that she participates in clubs or associations or works within her municipality, and that she has been living in her municipality for at least 10 years. Based on the score, the dummy variable *highplaceID* was constructed to take on the value 1 if the respondent's score was above the median score, and 0 otherwise.

To capture potential **crowding effects** of government-level policies on respondents' intended investment in RECs, we asked respondents to indicate their level of agreement with the following statement on a five-point scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5): "*If you think about how the sustainable energy transition is being implemented, how satisfied are you with the current performance of the French government?*" A similar item has been used in the German "Social Sustainability Barometer for the Energiewende" (Wolf, 2020). The dummy variable *unsatisfied* was coded to take on the value 1 if the level of agreement with the statement was below the median level, and 0 otherwise.

For some participants, gaining **independence** from their electricity provider might be an important motivational factor to become a member of a REC. To test for such an effect, we asked respondents to indicate their level of agreement with the following statement on a five-point scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5): "*I would like to be more independent from my energy provider.*" The dummy variable *independence* was coded to take on the value 1 if the level of agreement with the statement was above the median level, and 0 otherwise.

Finally, based on the screening questions and an additional question on respondents' level of education, a set of dummy variables was created taking on the value 1 if respondents were, respectively, female (*female*), below the age of 35 (*below35*), above the age of 65 (*above64*), in their country's lowest income category (*lowincome*), in their country's highest income category (*highincome*), or holding a higher education degree (*higheduc*), and 0 otherwise. We include these **socio-demographic variables** as control variables to mitigate potential omitted variable bias in our analysis.

Table 8: Individual-specific variables

Variable	Description	% of observations with variable equal to 1
<i>highenvID</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's score on a four-item environmental identity Likert scale is above the median, 0 otherwise.	49.5
<i>env_social_crit</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent ranks environmental and/or social/ethical criteria among her top three investment criteria, 0 otherwise.	23.1
<i>riskaverse</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's self-declared willingness to take risks is below the median, 0 otherwise.	33.9
<i>lowfinlit</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's number of correct responses to three financial literacy questions is below the median, 0 otherwise.	46.0
<i>sust_invest</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent has previously invested in sustainable investment assets or crowdfunding projects or in renewable energy cooperatives, 0 otherwise.	11.6
<i>social_norms</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's perception of social pressure to participate in sustainable financial investments (measured using three items) is above the median, 0 otherwise	33.8
<i>pos_reciprocity</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's self-declared willingness to return favours is above the median, 0 otherwise.	54.5
<i>highplaceID</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's integration with her local community (measured using four questions) is above the median, 0 otherwise.	33.9
<i>unsatisfied</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's satisfaction with their national government's implementation of the energy transition is below the median, 0 otherwise.	24.4
<i>independence</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's desire to be independent from their energy provider is above the median, 0 otherwise.	57.2
<i>female</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent is female, 0 otherwise.	50.1
<i>below35</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent is below the age of 35, 0 otherwise.	17.7
<i>above64</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent is above the age of 64, 0 otherwise.	27.0
<i>lowincome</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's monthly household income after tax is below 2,000 EUR (FR, DE), or below 3,000 PLN (PL), 0 otherwise.	37.2
<i>highincome</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's monthly household income after tax is above 4,000 EUR	22.4
<i>higheduc</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent holds a higher education degree, 0 otherwise.	53.4

4.4 Results

In this section, we document and discuss our findings of the fixed-effects logit model. Table 9Table 4 displays the estimated average discrete and marginal effects, i.e., the change in the average probability that a respondent chooses REC option A or B over the opt-out option in response to a one-unit increase in the referenced variable.

On average, respondents chose the opt-out option over option A or option B in 31% of cases. Moreover, about 79% of respondents chose to invest in at least one of the 16 options shown to them in eight choice sets. Thus, in general, the participants in our demographically representative sample appear to have a high interest in investing in the energy cooperatives shown in our DCE.

We report the coefficients of the latent utility function in equation (1) in Table A3 in the Appendix. First, we first present and discuss the results for the attributes of the DCE. Then, we present and discuss the findings for the variables reflecting preferences, capabilities, and social factors. Finally, we briefly describe the results for the socio-demographic factors.

4.4.1 Attributes

Our first finding in Table 9 suggests that higher **rates of return** increase respondents' propensity to invest in energy cooperatives. This finding is little surprising and in line with previous literature (e.g. Vuichard et al., 2019; Pons-Seres de Brauwer and Cohen, 2020; Cohen et al., 2021). The point estimate of the marginal effect implies that an increase in the rate of return by one percentage point increases the probability of choosing either energy cooperative option A or option B over the opt-out response by about 2.9 percentage points. To discuss the findings for the other attributes, we estimate the marginal willingness to pay (WTP) in terms of the change in the rate of return in response to a one-unit changes in the attribute levels. Thus, our WTP measure reflects participant willingness to trade-off rate of return against other attributes in the DCE. Following equation (5), the marginal WTP is estimated as $\frac{-\beta_k}{\beta_r}$ where β_r is the estimated coefficient associated with the rate of return, and β_k is the estimated coefficient associated with attribute k (as reported in Table A3). In *** p-value < 0.01, ** p-value <0.05, * p-value<0.1

Table 10 we report the WTP estimates together with the 95% confidence interval assuming asymptotic normality of $\frac{-\beta_k}{\beta_r}$.

Table 9: Estimated average discrete and marginal effects of attribute and respondent-specific variables on the probability of choosing an energy cooperative over the opt-out option

	marginal effect	p-value
Attributes		
<i>rate</i>	0.029***	0.000
<i>municipality</i>	-0.002	0.869
<i>firms</i>	-0.037***	0.002
<i>capital_cont</i>	-0.047***	0.000
<i>delegation</i>	0.022***	0.001
<i>self35</i>	0.089***	0.000
<i>self70</i>	0.118***	0.000
Individual-specific variables		
<i>highenvID</i>	0.042	0.123
<i>env_social_crit</i>	0.111***	0.001
<i>riskaverse</i>	0.018	0.500
<i>lowfinlit</i>	-0.165***	0.000
<i>sust_invest</i>	0.118**	0.034
<i>social_norms</i>	0.145***	0.000
<i>pos_reciprocity</i>	-0.029	0.265
<i>highplacID</i>	0.018	0.525
<i>unsatisfied</i>	-0.070**	0.019
<i>independence</i>	0.147***	0.000
<i>female</i>	-0.025	0.339
<i>below35</i>	0.146***	0.000
<i>above64</i>	-0.065**	0.024
<i>lowincome</i>	-0.083***	0.005
<i>highincome</i>	0.028	0.411
<i>higheduc</i>	-0.008	0.775
<i>Number of participants</i>	1,022	
<i>Number of observations</i>	21,478	

*** p-value < 0.01, ** p-value < 0.05, * p-value < 0.1

Table 10: Estimated WTP for attributes in terms of rate of return

Attribute	Estimated WTP	95% confidence interval	
		Lower limit	Upper limit
<i>municipality</i>	-0.62	-0.80	-0.68
<i>firms</i>	-1.28	-2.02	-0.54
<i>capital_cont</i>	-1.64	-2.19	-1.09
<i>delegation</i>	0.75	0.25	1.25
<i>self35</i>	3.12	2.42	3.82
<i>self70</i>	4.12	3.24	5.04

The findings for *firms* imply that on average, participants dislike RECs where firms may own parts of the shares compared to a REC where only citizens may own shares. In comparison, we find no evidence that participants dislike **co-ownership** by municipalities. As shown in *** p-value < 0.01, ** p-value < 0.05, * p-value < 0.1

Table 10, participants are willing to give up 1.28 percentage points of return for RECs where firms cannot own shares. This result supports earlier findings by Ek and Persson (2014), Brennan and Rensburg (2020) and Cohen et al. (2021).

For *capital_cont*, our findings suggest that on average participants prefer a **one-member-one-vote rule** to a rule where voting rights are based on the capital contribution. This result is in line with a similar finding by Sagebiel et al. (2014). Employing a one-member-one-vote rule rather than a rule where voting rights are based on capital contribution increases the likelihood that a participant chooses an energy project rather than the opt-out option in our DCE by 4.7 percentage points. As implied by *** p-value < 0.01, ** p-value < 0.05, * p-value < 0.1

Table 10 shows, for the average participant, the 'cost' of a capital-based voting rule compared to a one-member-one-vote rule would be about 1.7 percentage points of the rate of return.

For *delegation*, we find that on average participants prefer to have the **possibility to delegate their voting rights to a proxy** rather than having to participate personally in the general assembly. The option to delegate increases the probability that a respondent chooses energy cooperative options A or B instead of the opt-out option by 2.2 percentage points. Put differently, respondents are willing to give up 0.75 percentage points of the rate of return on their investment to be able to delegate their voting rights. This finding suggests that for the average respondent in our sample the transaction costs associated with participating in these meetings typically outweigh the benefits of active involvement in the governance of the REC.

Finally, the results for *self35* and *self70* suggest that respondents prefer higher shares of **self-consumption**. Because in our experiment self-consumption of electricity is assumed to leave the electricity bill unchanged, this result suggests that on average, respondents enjoy non-monetary benefits from using the electricity generated by 'their' REC. The effect sizes of these non-monetary effects are substantial. The ability to be able to self-consume 35% (70%) of a household's electricity consumption increases the propensity to invest in an energy cooperative by 8.9 (11.8) percentage points. Thus, participants appear to exhibit decreasing non-monetary returns to shares of self-consumption. Similarly, as reported in *** p-value < 0.01, ** p-value < 0.05, * p-value < 0.1

Table 10, on average, participants are willing to give up about 3 (4) percentage points of the rate of return to be able to self-consume 35% (70%) of their household's electricity consumption.

4.4.2 Individual-specific variables

Looking first at the results for preferences, we find that respondents with an above-median score of **environmental identity** are 4.2 percentage points more likely to invest in a REC shown in the DCE than to choose the opt-out option. Because RECs lower greenhouse gas and other emissions, this finding is little surprising and in line with the empirical literature analysing

investments in RECs/energy communities (e.g. Kalkbrenner and Rosen, 2016; Koirala et al., 2018; Cohen et al., 2021; Fischer et al., 2021). Similarly, we find that respondents who rank environmental and/or social/ethical criteria among their **top three investment criteria** are 11.1 percentage points more likely to invest in a REC than to opt out.

Similar to Fischer et al. (2021), we fail to find a statistically significant relation between **risk aversion** and intended investment in the energy cooperatives shown in our DCE. We note that for France, risk aversion was statistically significant in the DCE on investments in renewable electricity generation projects in section 3, which includes as an attribute the probability of a total loss. This difference in findings for comparable samples highlights that findings on the role of individual characteristics for (stated) investments in similar projects, cannot easily be compared across studies when attributes or attribute levels differ across these projects.

Further, our results on the role of capabilities imply that respondents with an above-median score of **financial literacy** in the sample are 16.5 percentage points more likely to state to that they would invest in an energy cooperative as shown in our DCE than to opt out. This finding is in line with the scant literature using a similar score to analyse the relation between financial literacy and investment in RECs (Fischer, 2021) and in sustainable financial investments (Gutsche et al., 2021). Likewise, and similar to Fischer et al. (2021), we find that respondents who previously invested in sustainable investment assets or crowdfunding projects or in renewable energy cooperatives are more likely to choose an energy cooperative option than to opt out. The effect size of 11.8 percentage points implies that such **prior experience** plays an important role in this context.

Considering the role of social factors next, we observe that **social norms** are statistically significantly and positively related with the probability that an energy cooperative option is chosen. This result parallels earlier findings by Kalkbrenner and Roosen (2016) and Fischer et al. (2021) in the context of RECs and by Riedl and Smeets (2017) and Gutsche et al. (2019) in the context of sustainable financial investments. More specifically, respondents whose perception of social pressure to participate in sustainable financial investments is above the median are 14.5 percentage points more likely to choose an energy cooperative option than to opt out. Next, in contrast to the DCE on investments in renewable electricity generation projects in section 4, we find no evidence that **reciprocity preferences** are related with the probability that respondents choose an investment option. This finding strengthens our explanation for our finding on the role of reciprocity preferences in section 3, which we relate to the fact that the DCE in section 3 includes as an attribute matching by the municipality. Further, we fail to find a relation between **place identity** and respondents' stated propensity to invest in an energy cooperative. This finding again differs from the finding on place identity for the DCE in France in section 3. A possible explanation for this difference could be that the DCE in section 3 included as an attribute the use of profits to finance nature conservation measures or to support low-income households in the respondent's municipality. In contrast, the DCE on RECs described in this section does not include attributes referring directly to benefits for the local community.

We further find that respondents who are **not satisfied** with the French government's implementation of the sustainable energy transition are less likely to choose an investment option for an energy cooperation. This finding is consistent with the literature on motivational

crowding (Nyborg and Rege, 2003; Frey and Stutzer, 2008) and suggests that government policy promoting the energy transition may spur additional investments in energy cooperatives by citizens. The effect size of 7 percentage points further implies that government policy in France may have meaningful crowding-in effects.

Finally, we observe that respondents who more strongly agree with the statement “*I would like to be more independent from my energy provider*” are also more likely to choose a REC over the opt-out option. Since most RECs in our DCE allow for self-consumption and thus allow members to gain **independence** from their electricity provider, this result is to be expected.

These above-described findings are derived while controlling for **socio-demographic characteristics** to mitigate potential omitted variable bias. We fail to find a statistically significant relation between gender and education with respondents’ intention to invest in the RECs. In comparison, respondents younger than 35 years are more likely to choose a REC rather than the opt-out option, while participants older than 64 are less likely to do so. For younger participants in particular, the effect size is substantial. Finally, we find that low-income households are 8.3 percentage points more likely to choose the opt-out option than medium-income households.

5 DISCRETE CHOICE EXPERIMENT ON ENERGY GAMIFICATION THROUGH MOBILE APPLICATIONS (GERMANY)

In this section, we present the DCE carried out in Germany on energy gamification through mobile applications (apps). In recent years, the number of mobile apps that encourage users to change their energy behaviours has been increasing. Many of these apps include gamification or serious game components to increase user engagement and salience of behavioural changes (Beck et al., 2019; Mulcahy et al. 2020). Through our DCE, we aim to better understand individual preferences for game design elements (namely social comparison and competition) in energy apps relative to preferences for other app features, different app developers and subscription fees.

In the following sub-sections, we first provide more details on the sample of participants in the DCE. Then we describe the DCE design, and report and discuss the results.

5.1 Sample

In Germany, 1,011 participants who indicated that they used a smartphone or tablet at least occasionally completed the DCE on gamification through mobile apps.¹⁴ Summary statistics for the sample are presented in Table 11 next to national population statistics for comparison. Overall, sample statistics are close to national statistics, though participants between 30 and 49 years are overrepresented compared to other age categories.

Table 11: Sample characteristics for participants in the DCE on gamification through mobile applications

	Sample	Population
Share of males^a	48.3	49.3%
Age (share of adult population)^b		
18-29	14.2%	16.5%
30-49	37.9%	30.3%
50-64	24.4%	27.3%
65 and older	23.4%	25.8%
Household income		
2,000 EUR or less ^c	29.5%	30%
2,001 – 3,600 EUR	31.1%	31%
More than 3,600 EUR	39.5%	39%

^a Source of population statistics: Eurostat (2020). ^b Source of population statistics: Eurostat (2019). ^c Source of population statistics: Statistisches Bundesamt (2018).

¹⁴ In total, 70 participants indicated never using a smartphone or tablet and were thus not eligible to take part in the DCE on gamification through mobile apps.

5.2 Discrete choice experiment design

To introduce the DCE on energy gamification through mobile apps, we used the following framing:¹⁵

*"On the following pages, we will show you different mobile apps to help you save energy in your daily life, participate in energy challenges, or inform you about projects and initiatives in the energy sector. We would like to know **which of these mobile apps you would like to use** if they were available to you.*

You may assume that all mobile apps presented to you are compatible with your mobile phone's operating system and are updated regularly.

*The mobile apps shown to you **all offer energy saving tips and allow you to track your electricity consumption to see how it increases or decreases over time.** If your home is equipped with a smart electricity meter, the app can be paired with the smart electricity meter and track your electricity consumption automatically. If your home is not equipped with a smart electricity meter, the app allows you to scan your electricity meter with your mobile phone."*

Participants were then asked to make a series of choice decisions between different mobile apps which differed by the following attributes

1. **Developer:** The mobile apps have either been developed by the participant's city or region, by a national public agency, or by the participant's electricity provider.
2. **Expert advice:** Some of the apps offer the possibility to exchange with energy experts to help identify the most effective ways to save energy on a daily basis.
3. **Compare and compete with other households:** Some mobile apps allow participants to compare their electricity consumption to the electricity consumption of similar households, while other mobile apps allow participants to take part in online challenges and compete against other households to reduce electricity consumption.
4. **Annual subscription fee:** The annual subscription fee to use the apps ranges from 10 cents to 6€.
5. **Use of subscription fees:** For some apps, the provider donates 50% of the annual subscription fees to fund nature conservation measures in the participant's region or to support low-income households in the participant's region.

The attributes and levels used in the DCE are shown in Table 12.

¹⁵ Instructions highlighted in 'bold ' were also seen highlighted in 'bold' by participants.

Table 12: Levels of different attributes considered in the DCE on energy gamification through mobile applications

Attribute	Levels	Variable	Type
Developer	your city or region, national public agency, your electricity provider;	(baseline) <i>agency provider</i>	dummy dummy
Expert advice	no, yes;	(baseline) <i>advice</i>	dummy
Compare and compete with other households	no, compare your electricity consumption to similar households, participate in online challenges and compete against similar households;	(baseline) <i>comparison</i> <i>competition</i>	dummy dummy
Annual subscription fee	10 cents, 2 EUR, 4 EUR, 6 EUR;	<i>fee</i>	continuous
Use of subscription fee	no donation, 50% are donated to finance nature conservation measures in your region, 50% are donated to support low-income households in your region;	(baseline) <i>nature lowincome</i>	dummy dummy

As in the previous DCEs, we employed a Bayesian-efficient design (Sándor and Wedel, 2001) to limit the number of choice sets shown to participants and to increase the efficiency of the DCE design. The priors used for the design were obtained from a second pre-test with 50 participants in the UK using Prolific Academic. The final DCE consisted of 24 choice sets divided into 3 blocks. In each choice set, participants were shown two mobile apps that differed in the attributes described above.

Figure 3 shows an example of a choice set used in the DCE.

Which of the following mobile apps would you like to download?

Please consider thoroughly that you actually are willing to download the mobile app when making your decisions.

	Mobile app A	Mobile app B
Developer	your city or region	national public agency
Expert advice	yes	no
Compare and compete with other households	no	compare your electricity consumption to similar households
Annual subscription fee	2 €	4 €
Use of subscription fee	no donation	50% are donated to support low-income households in your region

I would like to download: Mobile app A Mobile app B None of these mobile apps

Figure 3: Example of a choice set in the DCE on gamification through mobile applications

To mitigate hypothetical bias in the DCE, we included again a cheap talk design: Prior to each choice task, participants were asked to consider thoroughly that they were actually willing to download the mobile app when making their decisions. Moreover, participants always had the possibility to choose an opt-out option, i.e. to not select any of the mobile apps presented to them.

Our choice of attributes and attribute levels was guided by the literature studying individual motives to download and use mobile apps related to energy consumption and behaviours. Participants were assumed to make trade-offs between the attributes based on their preferences for specific features of the mobile apps, including nudging and gamification components, the type of developer and annual subscription fees.

Nudges, i.e. subtle changes in decision contexts that lead to predictable behavioural changes of imperfectly rational individuals, have become a popular policy tool following the seminal works of Thaler and Sunstein (Thaler and Sunstein, 2003; Sunstein and Thaler, 2003, Thaler and Sunstein 2008). In environmental policy, so called 'green nudges' that aim at promoting pro-environmental behaviour are discussed and implemented increasingly frequently by policy-makers (see for example Schubert (2017) for a review on green nudges and their effectiveness). Many of these green nudges target changes in households' energy consumption behaviours, for example through changes in default electricity contracts (e.g. Pichert and Katsikopoulos, 2008; Sunstein and Reisch, 2014, Kaiser et al. 2020) or regular feedback on energy consumption (e.g., Seligman and Darley, 1977; Karlim et al., 2015; Aydin et al., 2018). Relating households' own energy consumption to the consumption of other households has been shown to lead to energy savings (Allcott, 2011; Allcott and Rogers, 2014, Allcott and Kessler, 2019), though there is mixed evidence regarding the effectiveness of **social comparison feedback** in the absence of direct monetary incentives (Myers and Souza, 2020; Kandul et al., 2020). In our DCE, we did not test the effectiveness of social comparison feedback directly but rather investigated whether the availability of social comparison feedback increases the propensity to purchase an energy app. For this purpose, we included comparison with similar households as an attribute level in our DCE. We expected that participants are eager to take part in social comparison – albeit to varying degrees (Gibbons and Buunk, 1999) – and thus generally prefer options that offer social comparison feedback over options that do not.

For some options, instead of including social comparison feedback as a feature of the mobile app, we included an alternative gamification component that involves **competing** with other households through the mobile app. The literature investigating the impact of different gamification components in mobile apps that target energy behaviours is still nascent. Early research suggests that game elements can positively impact enjoyment of energy apps and enhance behavioural changes, with challenges being particularly effective (Mulcahy, et al. 2020). Beck et al. (2019) find that gamification has a positive effect on user ratings of energy apps, but that gamification components other than feedback (e.g. challenges, leader boards, badges) remain largely underutilized in energy apps. Against this background, we investigate if the option to compete with similar households increases participants' propensity to purchase a mobile app, compared to social comparison feedback or to no gamification components.

The attribute **expert advice** was selected among three attributes that represented additional, non-gamified features of a mobile app related to energy behaviours. The other two attributes we had considered were ‘customizable reminders’¹⁶ and ‘information on participatory eco-initiatives’¹⁷. The three attributes had been identified based on discussions with SONNET researchers and a review of existing energy apps. A pre-test with 50 participants in the UK using the platform Prolific Academic showed that participants paid considerably more attention to the attribute expert advice compared to the two other attributes. We thus kept expert advice as an attribute in the DCE. The other two attributes were dropped to keep the choice tasks sufficiently simple.

Participants’ propensity to purchase a mobile app may also depend on the **identity of the app developer**. In our DCE, we considered three different types of developers: cities or regions, national public agencies, and utilities. National public agencies may develop energy apps as part of the digital tools used by governments to support national energy efficiency policy strategies (IEA, 2021). Similarly, cities or regions can use mobile apps to help them achieve sustainability goals through (long-term) engagement of citizens by means of gamification (Kazhamiakin et al. 2016). Finally, utilities use mobile apps to improve customer experience (see e.g. Moreno-Munoz et al., 2016; Mulcahy et al. 2020). Among other features, these apps most frequently include personalized support and energy saving tips (Moreno-Munoz et al., 2016) as well as consumption feedback (Beck et al., 2019). Preferences for different app developers may for instance be driven by trust. Przepiorka and Horne (2018) find that trust mediates the effects of utility companies’ behaviour on consumers’ willingness to use an energy app provided by the utility. In general, by using an energy app, consumers are giving consent that the app collects and processes certain information on household characteristics and behaviours, including, for example, energy consumption data. Giving consent for the use of energy data can be seen as an expression of trust (Véliz and Grunewald, 2018). Thus, if an app developer is considered less trustworthy, we would expect to observe a lower willingness to download the energy app.

Finally, we included a cost attribute in form of a **yearly subscription fee** in order to observe trade-offs between the attributes described above and costs. To avoid that those participants with low willingness-to-pay disengage from our DCE, we further included a charitable donation attribute: in some cases, 50% of the subscription fees is **donated** either to fund nature conservation measures or to support low-income households. In the literature, such charity incentives have been found to increase consumers’ willingness to pay for different products (e.g. Strahilevitz, 1999; Koschate-Fischer et al. 2012).

¹⁶ In the pre-test, the attribute was described to participants as follows: “Some of the apps send you reminders on what you could do to decrease your energy consumption (e.g. switch off the light or turn down the heat in rooms you do not currently use, turn off or unplug appliances that are not currently in use, etc.). You can customize the type of reminders you want to receive and how frequently you want to receive them (e.g. daily, weekly, ...)”

¹⁷ In the pre-test, the attribute was described to participants as follows: “Some mobile apps provide information on participatory eco-initiatives in your region and how you can get involved if you wish to (e.g. citizen or neighbourhood initiatives to save energy or other resources, raise awareness for the environment, ...)”.

5.3 Individual-specific variables

To investigate the role of individual characteristics on the decision to download an energy app, the DCE was followed by survey questions on respondents' environmental preferences, social factors and capabilities.

Variables are described in detail below. A summary is presented in Table 13. All survey questions used to elicit the respondent-specific characteristics are presented in Table A1 in the Appendix.

As in the previous DCEs, environmental preferences are captured via **environmental identity**. To this end, respondents were asked to indicate on a five-point scale to what extent they agreed or disagreed with four statements adapted from Whitmarsh and O'Neill's (2010) environmental identity scale. The items are reported in table A1 in the Appendix. Responses to the items were added up with higher values indicating stronger environmental identity, and a dummy variable, *highenvID*, was created that took on the value 1 if the respondent's score based on the four items was above the median score, and 0 otherwise.

Regarding social factors, we measure individual differences in **social comparison processes** using four items from the eleven-item Iowa – Netherland Comparison Orientation Measure (INCOM) (Gibbons and Buunk, 1999). The four items were selected to refer to comparisons of abilities rather than comparisons of opinions and to fit decision-contexts similar to the choice of an energy application with a social comparison feature as in our DCE. A shorter version of the INCOM scale proposed by Schneider and Schupp (2014) included three items to investigate differences in individual comparison processes of abilities; two of these items are also included in our scale. Answers to the four items, which are presented in table A1 in the Appendix, were summed up to form a social comparison score. A higher score indicates that the respondent has a stronger tendency to compare her own abilities with those of others. The dummy variable *social_comparison* was constructed which takes on the value 1 if the respondent's social comparison score is above the median score, and 0 otherwise.

Furthermore, we measured individual differences in **competitiveness** using items from Orosz et al.'s (2018) Multidimensional Competitive Oriented Inventory (MCOI). The MCOI consists of twelve items that are intended to measure four different aspects of competitive orientation: lack of interest in competition, hypercompetitive orientation, anxiety-driven competition avoidance, and self-developmental competitive orientation. In the context of citizens' propensity to use an energy app with a competition feature, we are particularly interested in the last aspect: self-developmental competitive orientation. The three items in our questionnaire thus correspond to the three items related to self-developmental competitive orientation in the MCOI. The items are described in Table A1 in the Appendix. For each item, responses were provided with a five-point Likert scale, where higher scale points corresponded to a stronger competitive orientation. Answers from the three items were summed up to form a competitive orientation score. The dummy variable *competitive* was constructed which takes on the value 1 if the respondent's competitive orientation score is above the median score, and 0 otherwise.

Similar to the previous DCEs, we measured respondents' **subjective social norms** by adapting three questions from Whitmarsh and O'Neill (2010) to match the context of the DCE. Specifically,

respondents answered the following questions: 1) *Do any of your family members, friends or colleagues use a mobile app to save energy or monitor energy consumption?* (Response options: Yes; No; Don't know); 2) *How much influence do your family, friends and colleagues have on your decision to use – or not use – a mobile app to save energy or monitor energy consumption?* (Five-point scale ranging from no influence (1) to large influence (5)); 3) *In general, what do you think your family's, friends' or colleagues' views would be of you using a mobile app to save energy or monitor energy consumption?* (Five-point scale from very unfavourable (1) to very favourable (5)). Based on these three questions we constructed a score that increased by 1 if respondents replied “Yes” to the first question, and if respondents chose a scale point above the median in the second and third question. The dummy variable *social_norms* was set equal to 1 if respondents' overall score was above the median score.

Looking at respondents' capabilities, we asked whether respondents had **experience using mobile apps** in general, and energy apps in particular. We further asked respondents if they had ever paid for a mobile app. 95% of respondents eligible for the choice experiment (i.e. respondents who used a mobile phone or tablet) indicated that they used at least some mobile apps regularly, and 9.6% of respondents indicated that they had already used a mobile app to help them save energy or monitor energy consumption. 35.2% indicated having experience with paid mobile apps. Since only few respondents indicated not using mobile apps regularly, we did not include an individual-specific variable based on this question in the fixed-effects logit model. Instead, two dummy variables, *exp_energy_app* and *exp_paid_app*, were created that took on the value 1 if the respondent had experience with energy apps or with paid mobile apps, respectively, and 0 otherwise.

As in the previous DCEs, we asked respondents to indicate their level of agreement with the following statement on a five-point scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5): *“If you think about how the sustainable energy transition is being implemented, how satisfied are you with the current performance of the German government?”* The question is intended to capture potential **crowding effects** of government-level policies on respondent's intended adoption of an energy app. The dummy variable *unsatisfied* was coded to take on the value 1 if the level of agreement with the statement was below the median level, and 0 otherwise.

Finally, to mitigate potential omitted variable bias, we included a set of dummy variables for **socio-economic characteristics** in our analysis. These variables took on the value 1 if respondents were, respectively, female (*female*), below the age of 35 (*below35*), above the age of 64 (*above64*), in their country's lowest income category (*lowincome*), in their country's highest income category (*highincome*), or holding a higher education degree (*higheduc*), and 0 otherwise.

Table 13: Individual-specific variables

Variable	Description	% of observations with variable equal to 1
<i>highenvID</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's score on a four-item environmental identity Likert scale is above the median, 0 otherwise.	47.9
<i>social_comparison</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's score on a four-item social-comparison orientation Likert scale is above the median, 0 otherwise.	47.6
<i>competitive</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's score on a three-item competitive orientation Likert scale is above the median, 0 otherwise.	52.7
<i>exp_energy_app</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent has previously used a mobile energy app, 0 otherwise.	9.6
<i>exp_paid_app</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent has previously paid for a mobile app, 0 otherwise.	35.2
<i>social_norms</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's perception of social pressure to use mobile energy apps (measured using three items) is above the median, 0 otherwise	34.3
<i>unsatisfied</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's satisfaction with their national government's implementation of the sustainable energy transition is below the median, 0 otherwise.	23.9
<i>female</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent is female, 0 otherwise.	51.6
<i>below35</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent is below the age of 35, 0 otherwise.	23;0
<i>above64</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent is above the age of 64, 0 otherwise.	23.4
<i>lowincome</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's monthly household income after tax is below 2,000 EUR (FR, DE), or below 3,000 PLN (PL), 0 otherwise.	29.5
<i>highincome</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent's monthly household income after tax is above 4,000 EUR	39.5
<i>higheduc</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if respondent holds a higher education degree, 0 otherwise.	35.5

5.4 Results

In this section, we document and discuss our findings of the fixed-effects logit model. Table 14 shows the estimated average discrete and marginal effects, i.e. the change in the average probability that a respondent chooses mobile app A or B over the opt-out option in response to a one-unit increase in the referenced variable.

On average, respondents chose option A or option B over the opt-out option in 46% of cases. Moreover, about 65% of respondents chose at least one of the 16 options shown to them in eight choice sets. Thus, in general, a majority of the participants in our demographically representative sample appear to have at least some interest in an energy app. Yet, this share is lower compared to the share of respondents showing interest in investments in renewable electricity generation projects (89%) or energy cooperatives (79%) in the two previously described choice experiments.

We report the coefficients of the latent utility function in equation (1) in Table A4 in the Appendix. First, we first present and discuss the results for the attributes of the DCE. Then, we present and discuss the findings for the variables reflecting environmental preferences, social factors and capabilities. Finally, we briefly describe the results for the socio-demographic factors.

5.4.1 Attributes

Our findings presented in Table 14 suggest that respondents, on average, prefer mobile apps **developed** by their city or region over mobile apps developed by a national agency. In terms of magnitude, the effect is small: the probability that a respondent chooses a mobile app over the opt-out option decreases on average by 1.9 percentage points if the app is offered by a national agency rather than by the respondent's city or region. In comparison, respondents are 2.5 percentage point more likely to select a mobile app in the DCE over the opt-out option if the app is developed by an energy provider rather than by the respondent's municipality or region. Similarly, looking at the WTP figures reported in Table 15 and calculated based on the attribute coefficients reported in Table A4, we find that respondents are willing to pay 78 cents per year more (60 cents per year less) for a mobile app developed by an energy provider (a national agency) compared to a mobile app developed by the respondents' city or region.

The positive and statistically significant effects for **comparison** and **competition** indicate that on average participants value these mobile app features, which is consistent with previous findings in the literature (Mulcahy et al, 2020, Beck et al. 2019). Similarly, the positive and significant effect for **advice** indicates that respondents' average propensity to download an app increases if **expert advice** is included as a feature. Albeit positive, effects of all three attributes are small in terms of magnitude. *Advice*, *comparison* and *competition* increase the probability that a respondent chooses a mobile app over the opt-out option on average by 4.6, 4.1 and 5.5 percentage points, respectively. Results in Table 15 suggest that respondents are willing to pay about 1.24 EUR and 1.67 EUR per year for these app features.

The marginal effect of *fee* is – as expected – negative and statistically significant, indicating that participants dislike mobile apps with higher annual **subscription fees**. An increase in the annual subscription fee by 1 Euro decreases respondents' propensity to select a mobile app by 3.2 percentage points. This finding is also consistent with the finding that only a third of the participants indicated in a follow-up survey question that they have spent money on a mobile app before.

Finally, participants are more willing to download a mobile app if part of the subscription fees is **donated** to either finance nature conservation measures or support low-income households – a

finding consistent with extant literature (Strahilevitz, 1999; Koschate-Fischer et al. 2012). The effects of discrete changes in *nature* and *lowincome* on respondents' probability to select a mobile app over the opt-out option are relatively large: 8.0 and 9.0 percentage points, respectively. Donations can thus offset the negative effect of (small) increases in subscription fees. In contrast to results from the DCE on investment projects in renewable electricity generation, comparing the coefficients for *lowincome* and *nature* in Table A4 using a Wald test, we find no statistically significant difference in preferences between donations to support low-income households and donations to fund nature conservation measures.

Table 14: Estimated average discrete and marginal effects of attribute and respondent-specific variables on the probability of choosing a mobile app over the opt-out option

	marginal effect	p-value
Attributes		
<i>fee</i>	-0.032***	0.000
<i>agency</i>	-0.019**	0.016
<i>provider</i>	0.025***	0.009
<i>advice</i>	0.046***	0.000
<i>comparison</i>	0.041***	0.000
<i>competition</i>	0.055***	0.000
<i>nature</i>	0.080***	0.000
<i>lowincome</i>	0.090***	0.000
Individual-specific variables		
<i>female</i>	-0.012	0.561
<i>below35</i>	0.126***	0.000
<i>above64</i>	-0.093***	0.000
<i>lowincome</i>	-0.015	0.557
<i>highincome</i>	0.026	0.273
<i>higheduc</i>	-0.003	0.907
<i>highenvID</i>	0.080***	0.000
<i>social_comparison</i>	0.057***	0.010
<i>competitive</i>	0.064***	0.003
<i>exp_energy_app</i>	0.067*	0.084
<i>exp_paid_app</i>	0.049**	0.037
<i>social_norms</i>	0.187***	0.000
<i>unsatisfied</i>	-0.037	0.105
Number of respondents	1,011	
Number of observations	24,822	

*** p-value < 0.01, ** p-value < 0.05, * p-value < 0.1

Table 15: Estimated WTP for attributes

Attribute	Estimated WTP	95% confidence interval	
		Lower limit	Upper limit
<i>agency</i>	-0.60	-1.11	-0.10
<i>provider</i>	0.78	0.20	1.36
<i>advice</i>	1.42	1.03	1.82
<i>comparison</i>	1.24	0.68	1.80
<i>competition</i>	1.67	1.09	2.27
<i>nature</i>	2.41	1.79	3.02
<i>lowincome</i>	2.73	2.07	3.37

5.4.2 Individual-specific variables

Looking first at the results for environmental preferences, we find that respondents with an above-median score of **environmental identity** are 8 percentage points more likely to choose a mobile app shown in the DCE than to choose the opt-out option. Because all mobile apps offer energy saving tips and allow respondents to track their energy consumption, this finding is in line with our expectations and with the empirical literature analysing the link between environmental identity and pro-environmental behaviours. Whitmarsh and O'Neill (2010), for instance, observe that 'pro-environmental self-identity' positively influences several pro-environmental behaviours including energy conservation. To our knowledge, the relation between environmental identity and adoption of energy apps has not been investigated in extant literature, however. Relatedly, in the context of travel apps that help users improve trip efficiency or promote green travel, Dastjerdi et al. (2019), find that environmental attitude positively impacts adoption intention.

Considering social factors, we observe that respondents who are stronger **social comparison-oriented** or stronger self-developmental **competitive-oriented** are 5.7 and 6.4 percentage points more likely to choose a mobile app over the opt-out option, respectively. Since all mobile apps presented in the DCE included either a social comparison or a competition feature, this result is to be expected. Furthermore, we observe that **social norms** are statistically significantly and strongly positively related with the probability that a mobile app is chosen. More specifically, respondents whose perception of social pressure to use mobile energy apps is above the median are 18.7 percentage points more likely to choose a mobile app than to opt out.

Our results on the role of capabilities imply that respondents who have **prior experience** with mobile energy apps or paid mobile apps are more likely choose an app in the DCE. The effect of prior experience with energy apps is only significant at the 10% confidence level.

The marginal effect of *unsatisfied* fails to be statistically significant at the 10% level ($p=0.105$). We thus do not find sufficient evidence to conclude respondents who are **dissatisfied** with the German government's implementation of the sustainable energy transition are less likely to choose a mobile app in the DCE.

The findings presented above are derived while controlling for **socio-demographic characteristics** to mitigate potential omitted variable bias. We fail to find a statistically significant relation between gender, income and education with participant intention to download a mobile app. In comparison, participants younger than 35 years are more likely to choose a mobile app rather than the opt-out option, while participants older than 64 are less likely to do so. For younger participants in particular, the effect size is substantial.

6 ASSESSMENT OF FUTURE POTENTIALS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR BUSINESS MODELS AND POLICIES

This section discusses the future potential of the analysed SIE types, business model implications, and policy recommendations. The discussion is based on the results from the statistical-econometric analyses presented in sections 3, 4, and 5. In addition, we use survey items included in the sample in France to assess the relevance of factors that would motivate participants to invest in a renewable energy cooperative in the future. Similarly, we use survey items included in the sample in Germany to assess factors that would motivate participants to download an energy app.

6.1 Renewable electricity generation projects and renewable energy cooperatives

Our findings suggest that around 90% of participants in France, Germany and Poland choose to invest in one of the projects shown in our DCE on investments in decentralized renewable electricity generation. Similarly, almost 80% of respondents in France choose to invest in at least one of the energy cooperatives shown to them in our DCE on RECs. These findings confirm earlier studies (Cohen et al., 2021) and suggest **a generally high interest in this kind of projects - and thus a strong future potential for their diffusion.**

Of course, our results pertain to projects shown in the DCEs and characterized by specific attributes and attribute levels. Results might have been different if projects with other attributes or attribute levels were presented to respondents, e.g. projects with lower rates of return or projects using specific technologies such as solar, wind or biomass. Moreover, despite the use of a strong cheap talk design, hypothetical bias in the DCEs could have led to an overestimation of the share of participants generally interested in the presented investment options. The shares reported above can thus be considered as upper limits for the share of respondents – and by extrapolation citizens in France, Germany and Poland – that have at least some interest in investments in renewable electricity generation projects.

Despite the high shares of generally interested participants, **it is unlikely that a majority of citizens will invest in renewable electricity generation projects in the near future.** In a survey question shown to all participants in the SONNET citizen survey, between 20 and 30% of respondents in France, Germany and Poland indicated that they were planning to invest in a green/sustainable crowd-funding project, in a REC or in green/sustainable investment assets – in addition to the 4 to nearly 15% who already did so (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Investment, Participation and Volunteering in SIE, Energy and Sustainability Activities¹⁸

That is, so far only a small share of respondents has previously invested in green/sustainable investment assets or crowdfunding projects, or RECs. This result is overall similar across countries, though a larger share of respondents in France (14.6%) and Germany (10.6%) than in Poland (5%) indicate that they have previously invested in green/sustainable investment assets. Overall, these figures suggest that **the potential for citizen participation in the energy transition through sustainable investments or RECs remains largely untapped.**

One barrier to citizen participation in renewable electricity projects could be ignorance of existing initiatives. In the sample in France, only 17% of respondents indicated they had heard about RECs prior to taking part in the survey. Out of those, only 27% indicated that they knew a REC in their region. This argument is further supported by findings from our DCEs suggesting that prior experience with sustainable investments is a strong predictor of citizen participation.

Results from our DCEs also shed light on business models and policy interventions that could help exploit the unused potential for citizen participation in renewable electricity generation projects in France, Germany and Poland, and more specifically in RECs in France.

Firstly, results from our DCEs show that **financial aspects such as rate of return are very important if not the most important attribute for citizen engagement** in these types of social innovation in energy. This finding contrasts with some results of earlier literature that focuses on 'early adopters'. It is also supported by Figure 5 which implies that factors such as 'having a say in local power generation issues' or 'being part in a local initiative' do not rank very highly compared to receiving financial benefits or supporting renewable energy production.¹⁹

¹⁸ Due to an error in the survey flow, 174 French participants were not asked if they had invested or were planning to invest in renewable energy cooperatives. These participants were excluded from the analysis for that question.

¹⁹ These findings are indicative. They support results from the DCE analysis but should not be overinterpreted.

Figure 5: Factors which would motivate participants to invest in a renewable energy cooperative as shares of participants selecting a particular factor (participants could select up to three factors)

Similarly, Figure 6 shows that in the French sample, two thirds of respondents agree or strongly agree with the statement “A renewable energy cooperative should be profitable”. Strikingly, only 4% of respondents disagree or strongly disagree with the statement.

Figure 6: Agreement or disagreement with the statement “A renewable energy cooperative should...” in the sample participating in the DCE on RECs in France

Our findings pertaining to the risk of total loss suggest that on average participants are very sensitive to the riskiness of the projects. Thus, **to spur citizen participation, project suppliers**

should provide insurance which ideally fully covers potential losses. In circumstances where private insurers fail to provide such insurance, municipalities or other public entities could stand in. In addition, public entities (or other trusted institutions) could provide credible information on the low chance of a total loss.

Recommendations for business models based on our DCE results also include lowering minimum investment requirements. Such a step is expected to improve participation of citizens in renewable electricity generation projects, i.e. increase the extensive margin. Yet, to which extent lowering minimum investment requirements increases the actual amounts invested also depends on the intensive margin. Spending profits on improving the local environment (rather than on supporting low-income households) can further improve participation of citizens.

Findings from the DCE on RECs conducted in France further provide mixed support for the so-called Consumer Stock Ownership Plan (CSOP).²⁰ The CSOP business model has recently been suggested and explored via various case studies in the H2020 project SCORE (Supporting Consumer Ownership in Renewable Energies) (<https://www.score-h2020.eu/>) (Lowitzsch, 2019). Complying with EU regulation on energy communities, a CSOP pools individual investments in an intermediary entity which takes out a long-term investment loan, thus using leverage to scale up the investment. This intermediary entity invests into a plant and operates it on behalf of different co-owners. The acquisition loan is repaid by revenues from the sale of energy; any profits are distributed amongst the co-owners. In contrast to conventional business models for consumer ownership, a CSOP permits co-investments by municipalities, small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) and other local stakeholders. Investment and voting rights of citizen investors are represented through a trustee regarding these investors. Thus, a CSOP avoids personal liability, enables citizens to acquire an ownership stake in a company and to become "prosumers". A CSOP therefore enables citizens which are capital-constrained to financially participate in the energy transition. Compared to conventional business models, a CSOP is scalable, involves more efficient and professional decision-making via trusteeship, and is hence believed to be more productive and competitive. The findings from our DCEs on RECs in France suggest that a CSOP may indeed spur participation by citizens, in particular if the minimum investment requirements are kept low. **On average, citizens prefer delegating their voting rights to a proxy rather than to participate in the REC's governance themselves. Hence, they are expected to welcome a trusteeship as foreseen in a CSOP. However, our findings also suggest that citizens will have to be compensated (e.g. via higher rates of return) for the fact that in a CSOP voting rights are proportional to shareholding. Similarly, citizens will have to be compensated if firms become co-owners, but not if municipalities become co-owners.**

Further results from the DCE on RECs conducted in France highlight that participants value high shares of self-consumption of the electricity generated by the REC. Non-monetary benefits from self-consuming electricity appear to be high, and to decrease with the shares of self-consumption. This finding is particularly relevant when compared to findings from SONNET WP3 and in particular the research report on energy cooperatives in France (Ranville and Vernay, 2020).

²⁰ These results are based on the survey implemented in France. It is not clear to what extent results could be transferred to other countries.

According to a French interviewee “in other European countries, REC manage to link energy production with issues of self-consumption or energy supplies in the region. In France we do not do that and as a result French cooperatives do not inspire in the same way” (Ranville and Vernay, 2020, p. 22). **Our results suggest that enhancing self-consumption – through a facilitating legal framework and integration of self-consumption in RECs business models – could considerably increase citizen participation.**

Based on further insights from the WP3 report on energy cooperatives in France (Ranville and Vernay, 2020), additional questions were included in the French citizen survey. These questions are intended to shed light on desirable characteristics and potentially successful business models for RECs that were not addressed in the choice experiments. For instance, we asked participants if RECs should focus on renewable electricity production or engage in other activities. Overall, **respondents seemed to prefer a focus on renewable electricity generation:** 62% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed with a statement pointing in this direction (see Figure 6). Moreover, results shown in Figure 6 suggest that only a minority of respondents agreed or strongly agreed with the statements that RECs should be led by environmental activists (33%) and that RECs should be based mainly on volunteer work (30%). When asked if RECs should (i) collaborate with private actors, (ii) only invest locally, and (iii) remain small enterprises, we found mixed results. Around 50% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed with the statements. Few respondents indicated disagreement or strong disagreement, but the share of undecided or “Don’t know” answers was found to be high. **These results suggest that most respondents are not fundamentally opposed to the idea that RECs collaborate with private actors, invest non-locally or grow into large enterprises, but that acceptance may depend on the concrete modalities of such business developments.** Finally, in terms of general image of RECs, results from a further survey question in France suggest that **respondents are more willing to invest in RECs that present themselves as innovative projects or citizen projects, rather than RECs that have an activist image** (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Responses to the question “In general, how willing are you to invest in ...” in the sample participating in the DCE on RECs in France

Going back to insight from our choice experiments, **considering (local) government interventions, our findings on matching and place identity in France, Germany and Poland indicate the role of municipalities to spur citizen investments.** That is, municipalities may help to increase participation in renewable electricity generation projects through matching funds (in France and Germany, but not in Poland) and by reinforcing citizens place identity (e.g. via

strengthening sense of community) (in France and Poland, but not in Germany). However, to which extent matching leverages additional resources by citizens depends on both the change in the number of citizens deciding to participate in a REC (extensive margin), and the amounts they invest conditional on participation (intensive margin).

Further, **our findings on financial literature and experience with sustainable investments indicate that offering educational measures fostering financial literacy and information on the return and risk performance of RECs compared to conventional investments would spur citizen participation.** Likewise, our finding on 'crowding in' suggests that communicating the success of government policies towards a sustainable energy transition would increase citizen participation (in Germany, but not in France and Poland). Finally, our results on socio-demographic factors suggest that persons younger than 35 years and with higher income are more likely to invest in renewable electricity generation projects.

6.2 Gamification through mobile applications

Around 65% of participants in Germany chose at least one of the energy apps shown in our DCE on gamification through mobile apps. These figures are considerably lower than the share of participants who selected at least one of the investment options in the DCE on renewable electricity generation projects (89% on average) and in the DCE on RECs (79%). **Our results thus suggest that interest in the type of mobile energy apps proposed in our DCE is comparatively weak, despite the low costs of the apps.**

One explanation for respondents' reluctance to choose an energy app in the DCE could be their **general reluctance to pay for mobile apps.** About two thirds of respondents indicated that they had never paid for a mobile app. At the same time, respondents who indicated having experience with paid mobile apps were more likely to select a mobile app over the opt-out option in the DCE. Based on these findings, we suspect that free energy apps might have a considerably higher potential in terms of citizen participation compared to paid apps. Unfortunately, our data does not allow us to further investigate this aspect.

While higher annual subscription fees decrease respondents' propensity to download a mobile app, the fact that part of the subscription fees are donated to fund nature conservation measures or to support low-income households has a positive effect on stated adoption. Indeed, results from our DCE suggest that charitable donations can more than offset the negative effects of an increase in subscription fees (at least for the amounts considered in our experiment). Thus, if subscription fees cannot be avoided altogether, combining them with charitable donations can be an effective way to increase citizen participation and profits.

In terms of further insights for business models, our findings from analysing the DCE suggest that **app features including nudges (social comparison) and gamification components (competitions) as well as expert advice all have positive effects of similar magnitude on participants' willingness to download a mobile app.** However, when participants were explicitly asked about features that would motivate them to download a mobile app, only a minority of respondents selected those features (see Figure 8). The share of positive responses was highest

for expert advice (28%) and lowest for competition against others (18%). **Other features not included in the DCE were perceived as more encouraging by participants. In particular, 59% of respondents indicated that receiving monetary rewards would encourage them to participate in an energy saving scheme using a mobile app, and 45% of respondents indicated that receiving regular updates on personal achievements would motivate them to take part in such a scheme.** The latter result provides some evidence that respondents prefer feedback on their personal achievements over social comparison feedback relating their achievements to the achievements of others. In general, it is likely that offering a variety of different features increases the attractiveness of energy apps. We would, for example, expect that people who are competitive-oriented react positively to gamification components, even if most people seem to have little interest in such features.

Figure 8: Responses to the question “To what extent would the following encourage you to participate in an energy saving scheme using a mobile app?” in the sample participating in the DCE on energy gamification through mobile apps in Germany

Our findings suggest that respondents prefer apps that have been developed by their electricity provider over apps developed by their city or region. Apps developed by a national agency are the least preferred. We can only speculate as to the reasons for these findings. One possible explanation could be that respondents expect energy apps developed by their electricity provider to be more performant (e.g. allow for better tracking of personal electricity consumption). Given our results, it might not be worthwhile for cities – especially small one – to develop energy apps by themselves because WTP is low, and the customer base is small in relation to the costs of developing such an app. For small cities these costs may be particularly large because they lack internal capacity to develop such an app. Since respondents react more positively to apps developed by their electricity provider than to apps developed by a national

agency, our findings suggest that electricity providers might be in the position to market mobile energy apps.

Finally, looking at individual characteristics, we find evidence that **mobile energy apps should be primarily targeted at younger people and – in the presence of subscription fees – at people that have experience with paid mobile apps.** Since social norms related to the use of energy apps also seem to spur adoption, **promoting apps within existing social groups (e.g. family, colleagues, members of clubs or associations, etc.) could also be an effective means to increase citizen participation.** Together with our findings on the positive valuation of interactive features (social comparison feedback, competition), the strong relation between social norms and decisions in the DCE suggests that peer effects can play an important role for adoption of mobile energy apps.

7 CONCLUSIONS

Based on a demographically representative citizen survey in France, Germany and Poland (total N= 6,141), this report assessed future potential of SIE in European countries. To this end, we employed statistical-econometric analyses to investigate factors driving citizen investment in renewable energy projects, participation in renewable energy cooperatives, and purchasing of mobile energy applications with gamification components. These analyses relied on three stated preferences discrete choice experiments (DCEs) and declarative survey questions. The analysis identified the role of specific attributes of these SIEs, and individual characteristics such as attitudes and socio-demographic factors.

Our results suggest a generally high interest in renewable electricity generation projects and renewable energy cooperatives. Interest in mobile energy apps with gamification components appears to be lower. Our findings highlight the importance of financial criteria for citizens' investment decisions. Individual capabilities, including financial literacy, preferences, including environmental preferences and risk preferences, and social factors, including social norms, are found to be strong predictors for respondents' decision to invest in a renewable electricity generation project or select a mobile energy app in our DCEs.

Our findings have direct implications for business models and policies. The observed preferences for specific attributes provide indications for business models that are likely to be more successful and/or should be enabled by policies. Our insights on individual characteristics allow to discern citizens who are more likely to engage in specific SIE types and to identify policies that could help increase citizens' willingness to engage in these SIE.

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Appendix 1: Additional material

Table A1: Survey questions used to elicit individual-specific characteristics.

Individual-specific characteristics	Questions/Items ^{a,b}	Response options
Gender	<i>Please indicate your gender</i>	Male; Female; Other
Age	<i>How old are you? (in years)</i>	Text entry
Income	<i>What is your household's approximate monthly income, after tax? (Please include income from everyone in your household from all sources, including wages, government and company pensions and benefits, and investments dividends, rents).</i>	FR: 0€ - 2,000€; 2,001€-4,000€; More than 4,000€ DE: 0€ - 2,000€; 2,001€-3,600€; More than 3,600€ PL: 0€ - 3,000PLN; 3,001€-5,900€; More than 5,900€
Education	<i>What is your highest level of education?</i>	No degree or certificate; Trade/vocational certificate or equivalent; High schools or equivalent; Higher education degree or equivalent (e.g. College, University); Don't know / no answer
Environmental identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>To save energy is an important part of who I am.</i> <i>I think of myself as an energy conscious person.</i> <i>I think of myself as someone who is very concerned with environmental issues.</i> <i>Being environmentally friendly is an important part of who I am.</i> 	Five-point scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5)
Investment criteria	<i>If you were to make a financial investment, which of the following criteria would be most important to you? (You can pick up to three criteria.)</i> <i>Financial returns; Financial risk; Liquidity (i.e. investment can easily be converted into cash); Environmental criteria; Social and/or ethical criteria; Type of product, service, or technology the investment finances; Benefits to the local community where projects are implemented (e.g. local employment gain); Participation in decision on how funds (proceeds) are distributed/invested; Transaction costs (e.g. fees, information gathering); A good understanding about the products/services/technologies the investment finances; Other; None of these criteria</i>	Multiple choice question (up to three choices)
Risk aversion	<i>In general, how willing are you to take risks?</i>	Five-point scale from completely unwilling to

Individual-specific characteristics	Questions/Items ^{a,b}	Response options
		do so (1) to very willing to do so (5)
Loss aversion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>I get easily attached to material things (my car, my furniture, etc.).</i> <i>I would have problems with having to move to a smaller place.</i> <i>I tend to keep old stuff around.</i> <i>I feel very bad if I lose something, even when it's not that important.</i> <i>I think I could cope losing all my belonging in a fire. (R)</i> <i>I would have no problem accepting a job that has less pay than my previous/current one. (R)</i> 	Five-point scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5)
Financial literacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Imagine, there are 100€ available on your savings account and the interest rate is 2% per year. In your mind, how much money will there be on your savings account after 5 years, assuming that you do not deposit or withdraw any money from your savings account during this time.</i> <i>Imagine that the interest rate for your savings account is 1% per year and that the rate of inflation is 2% per year. In your mind, how much will the amount of money on your savings account allow you to purchase after one year?</i> <i>In your mind, is the following statement true: "Purchasing a single company share typically involves a more secure rate of return than investing in a fund."</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less than 102€; Exactly 102€; More than 102€ (correct response); Don't know Less than today (correct response); Exactly the same as today; More than today; Don't know True; False (Correct response); Don't know
Experience with sustainable investments	<p><i>Have you ever</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Invested in green/sustainable investment assets?</i> <i>Invested in a renewable energy cooperative?</i> <i>Invested in a green/sustainable crowdfunding projects?</i> 	Yes; No, but I am planning to; No and I am not planning to
Social norms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Do any of your family members, friends or colleagues invest in sustainable financial investments?</i> <i>How much influence do your family, friends and colleagues have on your decision to invest – or not invest– in sustainable investments?</i> <i>In general, what do you think your family's, friends' or colleagues' views would be of you investing in sustainable investments?</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes; No; Don't know Five-point scale from no influence (1) to large influence (5) Five-point scale from very unfavourable (1) to very favourable (5)
Positive reciprocity	<i>If someone does me a favour, I am ready to return it.</i>	Five-point scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5)

Individual-specific characteristics	Questions/Items ^{a,b}	Response options
Place identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>I identify with the city, community and region in which I live.</i> <i>Did you vote in the last... ? (Please check all that apply.) Local election (e.g. city council, mayor); Regional election (e.g. regional parliament); National elections; Election of the European Parliament; None of the above</i> <i>Think of the municipality that you are living in and check all that apply. I am a member of one or more associations or clubs (e.g. for sports, music) located in my municipality; My workplace is located within my municipality; I am employed by my municipality; None of the above</i> <i>How long have you been living in your current municipality?</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Five-point scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5) Multiple choice question Multiple choice question Less than 2 years; 2 to 4 years; 5 to 9 years; 10 to 19 years; 20 years or more
Satisfaction with government action	<i>If you think about how the sustainable energy transition is being implemented, how satisfied are you with the current performance of the [French/German/Polish] government?</i>	Five-point scale from not at all satisfied (1) to very satisfied (5); Don't know
Independence from energy provider	<i>I would like to be more independent from my energy provider.</i>	Five-point scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5)
Social comparison orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>I always pay a lot of attention to how I do things compared with how others do things.</i> <i>If I want to find out how well I have done something, I compare what I have done with how others have done.</i> <i>I am not the type of person who compares often with others. (R)</i> <i>I often compare myself with others with respect to what I have accomplished in life.</i> 	Five-point scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5)
Competitive orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Competitive situations allow me to bring the best out of myself.</i> <i>I enjoy testing myself in competitive situations.</i> <i>I enjoy competition as it allows me to discover my abilities.</i> 	Five-point scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5)
Experience with mobile energy apps	<i>Have you ever used a mobile app to help you save energy or learn about energy topics?</i>	Yes; No; Don't know / no answer
Experience with paid apps	<i>Have you ever spent money on a mobile app?</i>	Yes; No; Don't know / no answer

^a (R) indicates items that are reverse coded.

^b Items for environmental identity, loss aversion, investment criteria, social comparison orientation and competitive orientation were presented in random order.

Table A2: Estimated coefficients of attributes and individual-specific variables for the DCE on investment decisions in renewable electricity generation projects

	France		Germany		Poland	
	coefficient	p-value	coefficient	p-value	coefficient	p-value
Attributes						
<i>rate</i>	0.1180***	0.000	0.1704***	0.000	0.0668***	0.000
<i>min_medium</i>	-0.1658***	0.001	-0.1278***	0.010	-0.0731	0.173
<i>min_high</i>	-0.3997***	0.000	-0.3215***	0.000	-0.1312***	0.009
<i>match_half</i>	0.0866**	0.031	0.1200***	0.003	0.0648	0.104
<i>match_full</i>	0.0591	0.139	0.3079***	0.000	0.0420	0.291
<i>loss</i>	-0.2490***	0.000	-0.2450***	0.000	-0.1818***	0.000
<i>nature</i>	0.1561***	0.000	0.0989*	0.037	0.0640	0.135
Individual-specific variables						
<i>female</i>	-0.1541	0.231	-0.1201	0.334	-0.1672	0.207
<i>below35</i>	0.5483***	0.002	0.1467	0.322	0.6605***	0.000
<i>above64</i>	-0.2274*	0.095	-0.4004***	0.008	-0.6339***	0.000
<i>lowincome</i>	-0.1384	0.295	-0.3498**	0.027	-0.0771	0.637
<i>highincome</i>	0.3609**	0.047	-0.1392	0.359	0.3302**	0.030
<i>higheduc</i>	-0.1399	0.273	-0.1190	0.374	0.1295	0.317
<i>highenvID</i>	0.3132**	0.015	0.1619	0.212	0.2231	0.103
<i>env_social_crit</i>	0.6424***	0.000	0.6679***	0.000	0.5877***	0.002
<i>riskaverse</i>	-0.4576***	0.000	-0.3325***	0.009	-0.2949**	0.034
<i>lossaverse</i>	-0.0713	0.575	0.1583	0.200	-0.0691	0.599
<i>lowfinlit</i>	-0.5614***	0.000	-0.5770***	0.000	-0.6578***	0.000
<i>sust_invest</i>	0.5359***	0.007	0.5040***	0.005	1.0124**	0.013
<i>social_norms</i>	0.7421***	0.000	0.6068***	0.000	0.3833***	0.007
<i>pos_reciprocity</i>	-0.2062	0.106	0.5620***	0.001	0.3086*	0.074
<i>highplacelD</i>	0.4971***	0.000	0.0610	0.665	0.4271**	0.012
<i>unsatisfied</i>	-0.1036	0.469	-0.2829**	0.039	-0.0478*	0.072
Constant	0.8237***	0.000	-0.0030	0.989	0.2759	0.272
LL	-6161.933		-5748.171		-5637.800	
BIC	12563.092		11733.548		11511.670	
Number of respondents	1,074		986		936	
Number of observations	21,328		19,606		18,700	

*** p-value < 0.01, ** p-value < 0.05, * p-value < 0.1

Table A3: Estimated coefficients of attributes and individual-specific variables for the DCE on renewable energy cooperatives

	coefficient	p-value
Attributes		
<i>rate</i>	0.1443***	0.000
<i>municipality</i>	-0.0089	0.869
<i>firms</i>	-0.1845***	0.002
<i>capital_cont</i>	-0.2370***	0.000
<i>delegation</i>	0.1083***	0.001
<i>self35</i>	0.4506***	0.000
<i>self70</i>	0.5975***	0.000
Individual-specific variables		

	coefficient	p-value
<i>female</i>	-0.1265	0.337
<i>below35</i>	0.7387***	0.000
<i>above64</i>	-0.3253**	0.024
<i>lowincome</i>	-0.4126***	0.005
<i>highincome</i>	0.1397	0.410
<i>higheduc</i>	-0.0379	0.776
<i>highenvID</i>	0.2079	0.121
<i>env_social_crit</i>	0.5507***	0.001
<i>riskaverse</i>	0.0905	0.501
<i>lowfinlit</i>	-0.8024***	0.000
<i>sust_invest</i>	0.5923**	0.039
<i>social_norms</i>	0.7054***	0.000
<i>pos_reciprocity</i>	-0.1448	0.266
<i>highplaceID</i>	0.0908	0.525
<i>unsatisfied</i>	-0.3495**	0.019
<i>independence</i>	0.7130***	0.000
Constant	-0.8355***	0.000
LL	-6245.883	
BIC	12731.161	
Number of respondents	1,022	
Number of observations	21,478	

*** p-value < 0.01, ** p-value < 0.05, * p-value < 0.1

Table A4: Estimated coefficients of attributes and individual-specific variables for the DCE on gamification through mobile apps

	coefficient	p-value
Attributes		
<i>fee</i>	-0.1860***	0.000
<i>agency</i>	-0.1123**	0.016
<i>provider</i>	0.1451***	0.009
<i>advice</i>	0.2649***	0.000
<i>comparison</i>	0.2307***	0.000
<i>competition</i>	0.3114***	0.000
<i>nature</i>	0.4479***	0.000
<i>lowincome</i>	0.5072***	0.000
Individual-specific variables		
<i>female</i>	-0.0696	0.561
<i>below35</i>	0.6666***	0.000
<i>above64</i>	-0.5495***	0.000
<i>lowincome</i>	-0.0854	0.559
<i>highincome</i>	0.1508	0.270
<i>higheduc</i>	-0.0144	0.907
<i>highenvID</i>	0.4544***	0.000
<i>social_comparison</i>	0.3195***	0.009
<i>competitive</i>	0.3641***	0.002
<i>exp_energy_app</i>	0.3671*	0.072
<i>exp_paid_app</i>	0.2756**	0.032
<i>social_norms</i>	0.9667***	0.000

	coefficient	p-value
<i>unsatisfied</i>	-0.2163	0.112
Constant	-1.9515***	0.000
LL	-6513.499	
BIC	13249.626	
Number of respondents	1,011	
Number of observations	24,822	

*** p-value < 0.01, ** p-value <0.05, * p-value<0.1

Appendix 2: EC summary requirements

Changes with respect to the DoA

N/A

Dissemination and uptake

Preliminary results from D5.4 were presented together with key findings from D5.3 at the Energy Talks Disentis 2022 (online). Key findings from D5.4 will also be presented and discussed at the SONNET final conference in Antwerp.

Deliverables D5.4 and D5.3. will be the basis of three to four academic papers to be presented at academic conferences and eventually submitted to peer-reviewed academic international journals. A working paper based on selected findings from D5.4 has been submitted for presentation at a special session at the EAERE conference 2022.

Deliverable D5.4, the full survey, and the data sets (that do not contain any identifying information) will be made publicly available on the SONNET website and / or Zenodo.

Short Summary of results (<250 words)

Based on the demographically representative citizen survey in France, Germany and Poland, this report assesses the future potential of SIE in European countries. To this end, it employs statistical-econometric analyses to investigate factors driving citizen investment in renewable energy projects, participation in renewable energy cooperatives, and purchasing of mobile energy applications with gamification components. These analyses rely in particular on 3 stated preferences discrete choice experiments (DCEs) and identify the role of specific attributes of investigated SIEs, and individual characteristics such as attitudes and socio-demographic factors.

Our results suggest a generally high interest in renewable electricity generation projects and renewable energy cooperatives. Interest in mobile energy apps with gamification components appears to be lower. Our findings highlight the importance of financial criteria for citizens' investment decisions. Individual capabilities, including financial literacy, preferences, including environmental preferences and risk preferences, and social factors, including social norms, are found to be strong predictors for respondents' decision to invest in a renewable electricity generation project or select a mobile energy app in our DCEs.

Our findings have direct implications for business models and policies. The observed preferences for specific attributes provide indications for business models that are likely to be more successful and/or should be enabled by policies. Our insights on individual characteristics allow to discern citizens who are more likely to engage in specific SIE types and to identify policies that could help increase citizens' willingness to engage in these SIE.

Evidence of accomplishment

This Deliverable and associated documents